

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

“Statistics-Driven Texture Sound Synthesis Using Differentiable Digital Signal Processing-Based Architectures”

Esteban Gutiérrez

Supervisor: Lonce Wyse

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Abstract

This thesis investigates the application of Differentiable Digital Signal Processing (DDSP) architectures to the synthesis and control of texture sounds. Texture sound synthesis presents unique challenges due to the complex, non-pitched and noisy nature of these sounds, which differ significantly from pitched instrument timbres for which DDSP was originally designed. The core of this research consists in developing novel differentiable signal processors and loss functions tailored to the characteristics of texture sounds, and integrating these innovations into DDSP-based frameworks.

Two synthesizers are introduced: the **SubEnv Synth**, which imposes amplitude envelopes in a subband decomposition of white noise; and the **P-VAE Synth**, which combines a Poisson process with a Variational Autoencoder (VAE) to deal with time and events respectively. This approach is directly inspired by Saint-Arnaud’s original conception of texture sounds. Additionally, the **TextStat** loss function, designed to compare texture sounds based on their statistical properties rather than short-term perceptual similarity, is also presented. This loss function is strongly inspired by McDermott and Simoncelli’s work.

The thesis details the implementation of two DDSP-based architectures incorporating these synthesizers and the **TextStat** loss function. Results demonstrate that the **SubEnv Synth** successfully resynthesizes texture sounds with some success, while the **P-VAE Synth** faces learning challenges. These challenges might be related to its VAE module’s complexity, however more research is needed to make this claim. Additionally, this research explores model variations that show potential for improved performance and suggests future work including the optimization of the **TextStat** loss function, reconsideration of VAE use, and real-time implementation of the developed models.

Overall, the contributions of this thesis provide a foundation for advancing texture sound synthesis, offering new tools and insights for both theoretical exploration and practical applications in the field of audio signal processing.

Preliminary Notes

Introduction to Supplementary Materials

This thesis is accompanied by supplementary audio files designed to deepen the understanding of the concepts discussed. These audio files are referenced throughout Chapter 8: "Results". To access the full set of experiments and audio files, please visit the GitHub repository `ddsp_textures_thesis`. This repository contains a series of Jupyter notebooks that organize the experiments in a clear and structured manner. These notebooks rely heavily on the two other repositories mentioned in this thesis: `ddsp_textures` and `VAE_SubEnv`, which handle the actual computations for the models discussed.

Acknowledgments of Software, Audio, and Visual Material Used

In addition to the primary research, various software tools and materials were utilized to support the development and presentation of this thesis. Here, we acknowledge these contributions.

Software

1. Python [van Rossum, 1995]: Utilized for implementing all the algorithms and experiments discussed in this thesis.
2. PyTorch: Employed for deep learning-related implementations.
3. Librosa [McFee et al., 2024] and Numpy [Harris et al., 2020]: Provided inspiration for the implementation of certain algorithms in a PyTorch-compatible manner.
4. Ableton: Used for augmenting audio datasets.
5. Photoshop: Applied to create some of the figures presented in this thesis.
6. Drawio: Used for designing vectorized diagrams included in this thesis.

Audio and Visual Material

1. Fire sound ("Remco_de_Kluisenaar_001_Fire_burning_in_woodstove_-sparkles_vuur_kachel.wav"): Used for training and testing various models. Downloaded from Freesound, originally uploaded by remcodekluisenaar and under the *CC BY-NC 4.0* license.
2. Water sound ("BGSaSc Water Beach Ocean Waves Constant Splashing Rocks Many Small Waves Greece 16"): Used for training and testing several models. Downloaded from Freesound, originally uploaded by Profspiesser and under the *CC0 1.0 Universal* license.
3. Walking sound ("Steps: Slippers on Wood (Compilation)"): Used for training and testing several models. Downloaded from Freesound, originally uploaded by Sheyvan and under the *CC0 1.0 Universal* license.
4. Beatbox sound ("Beatbox#1.mp3"): Used for training and testing several models. Downloaded from Freesound, originally uploaded by bufu-labs.info and under the *Sampling+* license.
5. Signal image ("Sound waves vector illustration design template Free Vector"): Used to create some of the figures in this thesis. Downloaded from Vecteezy and uploaded by Setiyo Wibowo, under their proprietary Free License.

All sounds were modified to be suitable for use in this project. The edits were performed to enhance their suitability for the specific tasks they were intended for. The types of transformations applied to the sounds included pitch shifting, trimming, and filtering. Additionally, the images were also edited to be included in some of the diagrams in this thesis.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation and Research Question

1.1.1 Motivation

The synthesis of texture sounds has been a topic of interest in the field of sound design and audio signal processing for many years. Before the advent of machine learning, texture sound synthesis relied heavily on traditional signal processing techniques. These methods often involved granular synthesis, convolution-based approaches, or procedural algorithms, which, while effective, required extensive parameter tuning and were limited in their ability to capture the complexity and variability of real-world texture sounds. The manual crafting of these sounds was labor-intensive and lacked the flexibility to adapt to new and diverse audio textures.

With the rise of machine learning, particularly deep learning, the field of texture sound synthesis has experienced significant advancements. Machine learning techniques have introduced a new paradigm where models can be trained on large datasets of texture sounds, enabling them to learn intricate patterns and reproduce high-quality textures with minimal manual intervention. These methods have not only increased the efficiency of sound synthesis but also opened up new possibilities for generating and manipulating sounds in ways that were previously unattainable.

The introduction of highly efficient architectures, such as Differentiable Digital Signal Processing (DDSP), has further revolutionized the landscape of sound synthesis. Originally designed for tasks like timbre transfer in pitched instruments, DDSP and similar architectures have demonstrated remarkable capabilities in sound generation. However, applying these models to texture sounds presents unique challenges. Unlike pitched sounds, which have well-defined and meaningful features like pitch and timbre, texture sounds are often more complex, lacking clear harmonic structure and being more dependent on subtle, time-varying features. This complexity requires adapting or extending existing architectures to effectively capture and reproduce the nuances of texture sounds.

The motivation for this thesis is to explore the challenges and opportunities in texture sound synthesis. By utilizing machine learning and innovative architectures like DDSP, this research aims to push the boundaries of what’s possible with texture sounds. We’re addressing the specific difficulties of working with complex, non-pitched sounds and, ultimately, we hope to provide sound designers and researchers with more versatile and expressive tools.

1.1.2 Research Question

Based on the motivations discussed in the previous section, it is clear that while machine learning, and specifically the DDSP architecture, has significantly advanced the field of sound synthesis, challenges remain when it comes to synthesizing and controlling texture sounds. The original DDSP architecture was designed with tasks like timbre transfer for pitched instruments in mind, which involve well-defined and relatively simpler audio characteristics. Texture sounds, on the other hand, are inherently more complex, often lacking a clear harmonic structure and requiring the synthesis of intricate, time-varying features.

Given these challenges, the central research question of this thesis is as follows:

Can a DDSP-based architecture be effectively used to synthesize and control texture sounds? What modifications are required to adapt the original DDSP architecture for this purpose?

This research seeks to explore the potential of the DDSP framework in the domain of texture sound synthesis, identifying the necessary adjustments and extensions to the architecture that would enable it to handle the unique complexities of texture sounds. The outcomes of this investigation could lead to more versatile and powerful tools for sound designers, capable of generating high-quality texture sounds with fine control.

1.2 Objectives and Rationale

In order to address the research question and effectively apply DDSP architectures to texture sound synthesis, a series of specific objectives have been established. These objectives aim to develop new methodologies and tools that overcome the limitations of existing approaches, adapt to the unique characteristics of texture sounds, and validate the effectiveness of these innovations.

1.2.1 Objectives (What?)

To achieve the goals outlined in the research question, the following objectives were pursued:

1. Develop a synthesizer for generating texture sounds using amplitude envelopes

for a subband decomposition of white noise.

2. Create a synthesizer that generates texture sounds through a combination of a Poisson process to create temporal events and a Variational Autoencoder (VAE) to generate the sounds for these events.
3. Design a loss function specifically tailored to compare texture sounds in a meaningful way.
4. Develop two DDSP-type architectures incorporating the before mentioned synthesizers and loss function.

1.2.2 Rationale (Why?)

The rationale behind these objectives is grounded in addressing the specific challenges of applying DDSP architectures to texture sound synthesis. Each objective is aimed at overcoming the limitations of current methods and enhancing the ability to synthesize and evaluate texture sounds effectively. The reasons for pursuing these objectives are as follows:

1. The synthesizers are necessary because the original DDSP architecture uses a sinusoidal model driven by pitch and loudness, which is unsuitable for texture sounds, since in general these types of sounds lack a well-defined pitch and are characterized by their complex noisy nature. It follows that developing a different approach to sound synthesis is a must.
2. The new loss function is essential because typical loss functions for these architectures compare signals perceptually over short time frames. However, for two texture sounds to be perceived as similar, they need to be statistically similar over longer durations rather than perceptually similar in short frames. This requires a loss function that can capture the long-term statistical properties of texture sounds.
3. The DDSP architectures are developed to test the new synthesizers and loss function. These models serve as benchmarks for the introduced synthesizers and loss function, and their positive performance can provide a definitive answer to the research question posed. By integrating the new synthesizers and loss function into a DDSP framework, we can evaluate their effectiveness in generating high-quality texture sounds.

1.3 Structure of the Thesis

The structure of this thesis is organized into nine chapters. An overview of the contents of the following chapters is provided below.

Chapter 2: "Background" provides a comprehensive summary of the current state

of the art in texture sound synthesis. It begins by exploring early definitions of texture sounds and their historical context and significance. The chapter then reviews various successful models used for texture sound synthesis, including those based on traditional signal processing techniques and neural networks. Particular emphasis is placed on Differentiable Digital Signal Processing (DDSP), with a detailed overview of its principles and applications. This chapter lays the foundation for understanding the advancements and innovations introduced in the subsequent chapters.

Chapter 3: "Signal Processors" introduces and develops two novel types of signal processors to be integrated into the final layer of the DDSP architecture.

First, the **SubEnv Synth**, a synthesizer inspired by the Spectral Modeling Synthesis Tools developed by Serra and Smith, combined with synthesis principles from the work of McDermott and Simoncelli, is introduced. This synthesizer is specifically designed to create texture sounds by shaping the amplitude envelope of a subband decomposition of white noise.

Then, the **P-VAE Synth** is introduced as a direct implementation of the main definition of a texture sound provided by Julesz. It employs a Poisson Process to generate events and a Variational AutoEncoder (VAE) to synthesize the sounds associated with each event. This innovative approach aims to more accurately capture the stochastic nature of texture sounds.

Chapter 4: "Loss Function" begins with a discussion of the desirable properties for a loss function specifically designed for texture sounds. Based on these properties and inspired by McDermott and Simoncelli's work, it introduces the **TextStat loss function**, a novel loss function designed to characterize texture sounds using marginal statistics computed from biologically inspired auditory models.

Chapter 5: "Encoders and Decoders" starts with a discussion that highlights the need for a different encoder in an architecture aimed at generating texture sounds. It then rigorously defines the encoders and decoders used in this thesis.

Chapter 6: "Architectures" discusses the primary architectures utilized in this thesis. First, an architecture incorporating the **SubEnv Synth** as a signal processor, mirroring the original DDSP architecture in spirit, is developed.

Second, the Stochastic DDSP Architecture, a slight generalization of the canonical DDSP architecture specifically designed to train models using the **P-VAE Synth**, is introduced. This architecture includes modifications to accommodate the stochastic nature of the **P-VAE Synth**. These changes are necessary to ensure proper back-propagation and effective neural network training.

Chapter 7: "Creative Applications" explores the practical applications and potential uses of the models introduced in this thesis. The chapter first addresses the ability of these models to facilitate real-time synthesis, showcasing how they can be adapted for use in various interactive audio environments. It then examines

the concept of timbre transfer, discussing how the DDSP-based models handle this application when extended to texture sounds. By investigating these applications, this Chapter highlights the versatility of the proposed models and their capacity for creative sound design.

Chapter 8: "Implementation and Results" begins by detailing the implementation of all the tools introduced in this thesis. It describes the GitHub repository `ddsp_textures`, highlighting its PyTorch compatibility and the additional functions developed for the research. The chapter then moves on to present the results, starting with the use of the signal processors in a purely DSP environment. It continues by evaluating the `TextStat loss function` and showcases various trained models using the proposed architectures. Finally, the performance of both the classical DDSP and stochastic DDSP architectures is assessed and compared, with a detailed analysis and discussion of the results to highlight the strengths and limitations of each approach.

Chapter 9: "Conclusions and Future Work" summarizes the key findings of the research and discusses the implications of the results. It also outlines potential directions for future work, suggesting ways to further improve texture sound synthesis and expand the applications of DDSP architectures. This chapter aims to provide a comprehensive conclusion to the thesis while opening avenues for continued research in this exciting field.

By following this structured approach, the thesis aims to provide a thorough understanding of the synthesis model introduced here, particularly through the innovative use of Differentiable Digital Signal Processing architectures.

Chapter 2

Background

This thesis explores the synthesis of texture sounds using deep learning techniques. This chapter serves as a foundational review to ensure a clear understanding of the core concepts upon which the thesis is built. First, the definition of texture sounds through history is discussed. Next, a brief review of signal processing techniques used in the past for analyzing and synthesizing texture sounds is provided. Finally, a summary of contemporary and successful deep learning approaches in this domain is presented.

2.1 What even is a Texture Sound?

As stated in the introduction, the main goal of this thesis concerns proposing a set of deep learning-based models that can, at some level, synthesize some variety of texture sounds. It is then of primary importance to study the definition of these so-called texture sounds. The mere problem of defining these types of sounds is highly non-trivial and it has been delved into by several authors throughout the years. The common consensus is that this concept was born as a sound domain analogy for the previously introduced concept of texture in the visual domain. Sharma et al. made a review of the proposed definitions through history in [Sharma et al., 2022], and the main contributions are summarized in this subsection.

The earliest attempt to define texture was made in [Julesz, 1962] in the visual domain. In his article, Julesz proposed the so-called "Julesz conjecture", suggesting that humans cannot distinguish between visual textures if they have similar second-order statistics. Such conjecture was later disproven in [Caelli and Julesz, 1978], however it introduced a statistics-based paradigm that is used for many applications to this day. Since then, visual textures have been extensively studied and explored in various applications (see e.g. [Humeau-Heurtier, 2019]).

Moving on to the sound field, the earliest explanation of audio textures was put forth in [Saint-Arnaud, 1995]. In that paper, its authors defined audio textures as follows: "Sound textures are formed by the basic sound elements called atoms; atoms

occur as per a high-level pattern which could be periodic or random; the high-level parameters must remain the same over a long period of time; the parameters must be exposed within a few seconds and high-level randomness is acceptable as long as enough occurrences are present within the attention span."

Additionally, in [Saint-Arnaud, 1995], the relationship between potential information with speech and music, texture, and noise is established. This relation explains that the information content present in sound textures is greater than that in noise but considerably less than in speech or music signals.

In 1998, the first method in audio texture synthesis was proposed for the first time in [Rosenthal and Okuno, 1998]. In that article, its authors defined audio textures as a two-level representation, where the first level states that textures are made of atoms, and the second level explains all the probability-based transitions between atoms. The atom in the audio texture is the smallest unit present in the texture sound, such as a fire crackle in a fire texture sound or a raindrop in a rain texture sound. This definition will be of particular importance for the method proposed in this thesis. Additionally, Rosenthal et al. suggested that there could be more than one atom present in an audio texture. This idea, although reasonable, introduces the challenge of defining, detecting, separating, and categorizing the atoms from a given texture sound.

Year	Definition
1962	Julesz conjectured that humans cannot distinguish between visual textures with similar second-order statistics.
1995	Audio textures are formed by basic sound elements called atoms; high level pattern must remain consistent over time; greater information content compared to noise but less than speech or music.
1998	Audio textures are represented as a two-level structure: atoms and probability-based transitions between them; atoms represent smallest units of texture sound.

Table 1: Definitions of Texture in Visual and Audio Domains. Taken from [Sharma et al., 2022].

The definitions proposed before are quite broad and comprise sounds that can get arbitrarily complex. Some examples include the sound of wind, radio static, rain, engines, air conditioners, flowing rivers, running water, bubbling, insects, applause, train, church bells, gargling, frying eggs, sparrows, jackhammers, fire, cocktail party babble, shaking coins, helicopters, wind chimes, scraping, rolling, rubbing, walking on gravel, thunder, or a busy electronic game arcade.

In the last couple of decades, several new approaches have appeared regarding the texture sound synthesis task. In accordance with this, new paradigms and, of course, definitions have appeared, however, some key concepts like unpredictability in the short term and stability in the long term seem to be of common agreement. Regarding this, [Wyse, 2022] adds that "In sound art practices, textures break from the pitched and metrical patterns of the past. Their complexity and unpredictability

at one level combined with the sense of eternal sameness at another can be read as reflecting aspects of the last millennium of urbanization, technological advancement, the rescaling of time and space through travel and communication, and the recent disruptions to rhythms and patterns due to a pandemic."

2.2 Classical Texture Sound Synthesis

The synthesis of texture sounds have come a long run the last decades and several approaches have been proposed throughout the years. In this section some of the non deep learning based models that can either be used or were directly created with the purpose of texture sound synthesis are briefly explained. The selection here proposed doesn't pretend to be a list of greatest hits, but else it contains two works whose ideas strongly inspired the models proposed in this thesis.

2.2.1 Spectral Modelling Synthesis (SMS)

A set of analysis/synthesis methods that has seen widespread correspond to spectral modeling synthesis (SMS) proposed [Serra and Smith, 1990]. Such methods are foundational to the theory of analysis and synthesis of audio signals, and although not specifically designed for texture sound synthesis, the ideas here presented have been adapted over the years with different purposes and have proven to be able to encompass a wide variety of sounds.

The main idea proposed in SMS is to decompose the original audio into a sum of two signals

$$x(t) = d(t) + s(t),$$

where d correspond to a deterministic term and s to a stochastic term. The deterministic term can be built in various manners, however in any case it correspond to a sum sinusoids that can vary in quantity, frequency, phase and amplitude in time. More precisely, the determinisitic part is defined as

$$d(t) = \sum_{j=1}^N a_j(t) \sin(\phi_j(t)),$$

where $N \in \mathbb{N}$ correspond to the number of partials and a_j, ϕ_j are the amplitudes and instantaneous phase of the j -th partials in time. Note that with this notation, the frequency of each partial is intrinsic and can be computed by integrating the instantaneous phase.

With this definition, the deterministic part ensure the capability of the model to synthesize with certain accuracy a wide variety of pitched sounds. On the other side, the stochastic term is defined as filtered white noise, that is,

$$s(t) = (h * w)(t),$$

where w correspond to white noise and h is the impulse response of a time-varying

frequency-shaping filter. This definition ensure the capability of the model to add noise at will, which can help in a variety of scenarios. Some examples are the attack of a plucked string instrument and breath noise of a singer.

The main takeaway of this model is the simple but clever implementation of separation and conquer. In this scenario, the deterministic part together with its partials can be understood as an analogous of the definition of texture sound together with its atoms proposed in [Saint-Arnaud, 1995] discussed in the previous section.

2.2.2 Synthesis from statistics of the auditory periphery

McDermot and Simoncelli worked for at least half a decade in the study of the hypothesis that texture sounds can be captured by summary statistics that are time-average of acoustic measurements made in the peripheral auditory system (see [McDermott et al., 2009], [McDermott and Simoncelli, 2011] and [McDermott et al., 2013]). Such hypothesis is of course both a generalization and a refinement of the "Julesz conjecture" for the audio domain. The generalization part concerns to the fact that this idea doesn't only consider second-order statistics; and the refinement part concerns to the consideration of the human auditory perception.

Although their work focused on the study of a biological/perceptual conjecture, in order to test their ideas they ended up building a synthesis algorithm capable of recreate a wide variety of texture sounds and to the date is one of the most influential works in the matter.

The model itself consists on two steps: first computing a set of biologically driven (using auditory filters) summary statistics of a texture sounds; and then impose such statistics on white noise through an iterative process.

The statistics are computed through a rather convoluted process and inspired the definition of the loss function used in this work, so we shall explain it without much detail in this section (for a more accurate implementation of this, see Subsection 4.2).

First, the target texture sound is filtered by a cochlear filterbank, generating a subband decomposition. Cochlear filter responses (i.e., subbands) are bandlimited versions of the original signal, the envelopes of which are computed using the Hilbert transform and are further processed through a compressive nonlinearity.

This process yield a series of compressed envelopes, from which marginal statistics and cross-band correlations are computed. The latter, represents an already large set of statistics, however in their work, they argue that there is still need to go further and compute marginal statistics for a modulation filterbank decomposition of the already decomposed signal. Regarding this, the authors say that "A modulation filter bank is consistent with previous auditory models (Bacon and Grantham, 1989; Dau et al., 1997) as well as reports of modulation tuning in midbrain and thalamic neurons (Baumann et al., 2011; Joris et al., 2004; Miller et al., 2002; Rodríguez et al.,

Figure 1: McDermott and Simoncelli's statistics. Figure taken from [McDermott and Simoncelli, 2011].

2010)." Modulation filterbanks are mathematically just another type of filterbank that is applied on the Cochlear filter responses. This yields a series of subbands for each one of the subbands envelopes of the original signal. For these, once again their marginal statistics and cross-band correlations are computed.

A visual representation of the whole process can be seen in Figure 1.

The results of this process generates a set of statistics, namely the marginal statistics and cross-band correlations of both the compressed envelopes of the subbands and subbands of the compressed envelopes of the subbands (tongue twister, I know). These numbers are then imposed to white noise in an iterative process until they are similar enough to the measured statistics. The synthetic signal is initialized with a sample of Gaussian white noise and each cycle of the iterative process consists of Algorithm 1. The results yields by this model are surprising for a number of reasons. First, to some extent, they prove that the synthetic sounds built using only the summary statistics could be accurately recognized, which is somewhat proof of a weaker version of Julesz conjecture, one that requires (way) more marginal statistics than only similar second-order ones. Second, by computing the summary statistics on the envelopes of a subband decomposition, they intrinsically prove that the information necessary to resynthesize a texture sound lies exactly there, instead of other types of decompositions as the ones discussed in 2.2.1, that is, a partial type of decomposition. Finally, and since the synthetic sounds obtained by their model

Algorithm 1 Imposition Algorithm

- 1: The synthetic sound signal is decomposed into cochlear subbands.
 - 2: Subband envelopes are computed using the Hilbert transform.
 - 3: Envelopes are divided out of the subbands to yield the subband fine structure.
 - 4: Envelopes are downsampled to reduce computation.
 - 5: Envelope statistics are measured and compared to those of the original recording to generate an error signal.
 - 6: Downsampled envelopes are modified using a variant of gradient descent, causing their statistics to move closer to those measured in the original recording.
 - 7: Modified envelopes are upsampled and recombined with the unmodified fine structure to yield new subbands.
 - 8: New subbands are combined to yield a new signal.
-

were often realistic, they also managed to introduce a model with value as a pure sound synthesis model.

All the latter implications of McDemott and Simoncelli’s work were of great inspiration for most of the ideas that flow through this thesis and they shall be discussed in more detail in Chapters 3 and 4.

2.3 Neural Texture Sound Synthesis

Like many other technology-related topics, the synthesis of texture sounds has been significantly influenced by the application of deep learning. This section discusses two types of models: those that have already been proposed and, to some extent, can be considered successful in the realm of texture sound synthesis; and Differentiable Digital Signal Processing (DDSP), a relatively new architecture that has not been extensively explored in the context of texture sounds. Significant emphasis will be placed on this latter subsection, as it lays the foundation for the models proposed in this thesis.

2.3.1 Some Successful Models

In recent years, neural networks have shown incredible promise in generating audio textures. A number of studies have delved into this area, each bringing unique approaches to the challenges of audio texture synthesis. In this section, we briefly introduce some works that have indirectly influenced this thesis.

Antognini et al. (2018) in [Antognini et al., 2018], take techniques from image texture synthesis and adapt them to audio. They enhance the traditional Gram matrix-based approach by adding autocorrelation and diversity terms to maintain rhythm and produce more varied textures. Their experiments highlight the trade-off between diversity and quality in the generated audio, and they introduce a new evaluation metric called the VGGish loss. This paper plays a key role in neural audio texture synthesis by tackling the core challenges of creating diverse, high-

quality sounds.

Wyse and Huzaifah (2020) in [Wyse and Huzaifah, 2020], expand on neural audio synthesis by exploring a broader range of audio textures, like rain, wind, and scraping sounds. They stress the importance of new training data and modeling strategies that go beyond what traditional methods can offer. They introduce a growing dataset and a metadata management system tailored for audio textures. This work showcases how deep learning models can extend sound generation, creating textures that go far beyond the data they were trained on.

Finally, in [Wyse, 2022], Wyse (2021) takes a more artistic approach, focusing on how deep learning tools can benefit sound artists. He explores the intricate nature of audio textures, which combine long-term stability with short-term unpredictability. The paper presents four deep learning tools, each suited for different aspects of texture modeling, and highlights their potential in sound exploration and creative expression. This work bridges the gap between neural synthesis and sound art, showing how these models can be used systematically as artistic instruments.

2.3.2 Differentiable Digital Signal Processing (DDSP)

Previous to the introduction of Differentiable Digital Signal Processing, most methods for neural audio synthesis produced raw audio directly in either the time or frequency domain. Some examples of this include strided convolution models—such as SING [Defossez et al., 2018], MCNN [Arik et al., 2019], and WaveGAN [Donahue et al., 2019]; Fourier-based models such as Tacotron [Wang et al., 2017] and GAN-Synth [Engel et al., 2019]; and autoregressive waveform models—such as WaveNet [van den Oord et al., 2016], SampleRNN [Mehri et al., 2016], and WaveRNN [Kalchbrenner et al., 2018]. An issue with dealing directly with the signal, in either the time or frequency domain, is that there are, in a way, too many degrees of freedom. This might sound like a strength of these models; however, it can also be thought of as a missed opportunity, since they are not taking advantage of the knowledge that has been built over the past decades regarding: first, human perception and cognition, since there are too many sounds that are perceived as the same but have radically different representations in the time and frequency domain; and second, sound synthesis, since there is a large number of models that have been developed to synthesize a wide variety of sounds using semantically interesting parameters, sometimes in very optimal (in the sense of their computational complexity) ways.

The DDSP architecture was first introduced in [Engel et al., 2020] and proposed a partial solution to the problem discussed above by integrating digital signal processing (DSP) techniques. More precisely, the DDSP architecture includes at least one module containing a signal synthesizer using digital signal processing techniques. Such a module is known as a signal processor, and it is required to be differentiable to avoid problems when back-propagating. This module is placed as the last layer in the architecture, and it is typically combined with other signal processing-aware layers, like pitch and amplitude detection (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: The DDSP autoencoder architecture. Figure taken from [Engel et al., 2020].

In their original work, Engel et al. proposed several signal processors that can be used in their architecture and actually trained some models on violin synthesis using a Harmonic + Stochastic model derived from the work discussed in subsection 2.2.1.

One of the main perks of the DDSP architecture is its flexibility. In principle, in order to build a DDSP-based architecture, one only needs three ingredients: a set of features that would be used to drive the model, a signal processor that will bias the synthesis capabilities of the model, and a loss function that captures the complexity of the sounds to synthesize.

Recent advancements in neural sound synthesis have been impressive, as evidenced by several notable works. [Renault et al., 2023] introduced DDSP-Piano, a neural sound synthesizer that leverages instrument knowledge for enhanced performance. The concept of style transfer in neural audio is explored by [Steinmetz et al., 2022], demonstrating innovative applications in sound design. A comprehensive review of differentiable digital signal processing (DDSP) is provided by [Hayes et al., 2023], offering insights into current trends and future directions. Data-driven procedural audio, specifically for generating procedural engine sounds, is the focus of [Lundberg, 2020], showcasing neural audio synthesis capabilities. [Yu and Fazekas, 2023] presents a method for singing voice synthesis using differentiable LPC and glottal-flow-inspired wavetables, pushing the boundaries of vocal sound modeling. Lastly, [Diaz et al., 2023] delves into rigid-body sound synthesis using differentiable modal resonators, contributing to realistic sound generation in virtual environments.

Chapter 3

Signal Processors

As discussed in 2.3.2, the DDSF architecture requires a signal processor as one of its pillars. In this chapter, the two signal processors that will be used in the models introduced in this thesis are defined and thoroughly discussed. Additionally, since these models are to be used in a DDSF architecture, their differentiability will be discussed for clarity.

3.1 SubEnv Synth: A synthesizer based on McDermott and Simoncelli’s work

McDermott and Simoncelli’s work on sound texture perception was based on the idea that it can be fully characterized via statistics of the auditory periphery. To compute these, they proposed an algorithm that computes statistics based on perception models. More precisely, they used a filter bank inspired by biologically plausible auditory models. Their results suggest that the perception of texture sounds is mediated by relatively simple statistics of early auditory representations, presumably computed by downstream neural populations.

A rather obvious but important implication of McDermott and Simoncelli’s work is that a full characterization of a texture sound comes from understanding the amplitude envelope of a subband decomposition of the sound itself. Based on this fact, we introduce the **SubEnv Synth**, a synthesizer that synthesizes sounds by modulating the amplitude envelope of a subband decomposition of white noise.

3.1.1 Formal definition

A synthesizer based on modulating the amplitude envelope of a subband decomposition of white noise can be implemented in several ways. However, since we are interested in using such a synthesizer in a DDSF architecture, we must ensure that its implementation is differentiable (more on this in the next subsection). This might sound counterintuitive because it uses white noise, which is typically generated us-

ing stochastic processes that are non-differentiable. To solve this problem, we will fix one instance of white noise and use it as a source of deterministic randomness. This source must have certain properties to be used properly later on. This leads to the following definition.

Definition 3.1 (Seed) *Let W be white noise, $F = \{f_j\}_{j=1}^N$ a filter bank and*

$$F(X) = (f_1 * W, f_2 * W, \dots, f_N * W),$$

the subband decomposition of the stochastic process W through F . A seed, made from W and F , is defined as the (vector) stochastic process

$$S = \left(\frac{f_1 * W}{|H(f_1 * W)|}, \frac{f_2 * W}{|H(f_2 * W)|}, \dots, \frac{f_N * W}{|H(f_N * W)|} \right),$$

where H is the Hilbert transform.

Remark 3.2 *In practice, to compute a seed, white noise is discretely sampled, for example, from a white Gaussian noise process, and the Hilbert transform can be safely replaced by the Discrete Hilbert Transform.*

A seed is a source of deterministic randomness that can be used by the model. The seed also has the property that each of its components corresponds to a band of the decomposition whose amplitude envelope has been normalized. In theory, the process of amplitude normalization could alter the subband decomposition by changing the magnitude spectrum in arbitrary ways. In practice, however, this issue is negligible, so we can think of the seed as a fixed subband decomposition of white noise, with amplitude envelopes that are constant over time and equal to 1.

The importance of normalization lies in the fact that to impose an amplitude envelope on a signal with a normalized amplitude envelope, the only operation needed is multiplication. Therefore, given a seed, the only thing that needs to be learned to synthesize a given sound is the amplitude envelope of its subband decomposition under the same filter bank that was used to create the seed.

Different seeds will yield to radically different signal in the time domain. However, due to the nature of texture sounds and based on McDermot and Simoncelli's work, these sounds should be perceptually the same, since their amplitude envelopes are the same for a sufficiently precise subband decomposition (an empirical proof of this fact is discussed in 8.2.1).

Learning an amplitude envelope can be as parameter-expensive as learning the entire signal, and this would need to be done for each band of the decomposition. To address this issue, we took advantage of the fact that the amplitude envelope of a texture sound is generally not as eventful as that of a generic type of sound. This is based on the idea that the noisy nature of a texture sound is captured by the seed

in this model. Consequently, we will consider only amplitude envelopes that can be generated by trigonometric polynomials; that is, every amplitude envelope will be the result of an expression of the form

$$A(t) = \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} a_j \sin\left(\frac{j}{M}rt + b_j\right)$$

where a_j, b_j, M, r are parameters.

Using trigonometric polynomials can be advantageous for many reasons. First, by controlling the number of sinusoids M , one can generate arbitrarily complex amplitude envelopes (because of the density of trigonometric polynomials in L^2 over any bounded interval). Moreover, results derived from this expression have the natural property of generating continuous and differentiable (actually C^∞) functions that are also cyclic. This can be useful if we want to shift the function without producing crackling sounds. Finally, in the discrete domain, computing a trigonometric polynomial can be done in a highly efficient way using the Inverse Discrete Fourier Transform.

As a result of all the above, the `SubEnv Synth` is introduced as a synthesizer that uses Algorithm 2 to generate sounds.

Remark 3.3 *Observe that, since the goal is to generate amplitude envelopes, one must ensure that signals a_1, \dots, a_{N_F} are actually real signals. This can be easily verified by the fact that the N_F spectra generated in step 1 are conjugate-symmetrical complex vectors, so applying the IDFT to them will always produce a real signal.*

3.1.2 Parameter Extraction and Resynthesis

The `SubEnv Synth` is designed to ensure both optimal computational cost and differentiability. These two properties ensure that it can be used efficiently in the context of DDSP, allowing the parameters needed to synthesize a given texture sound to be learned with a proper architecture and training. That being said, this does not imply that this synthesizer cannot be used in pure DSP contexts. In fact, one could easily extract parameters from a given texture sound and use them to resynthesize it.

To extract parameters from a given texture sound, one could take advantage of the fact that we are using the IDFT to synthesize a subband decomposition of a sound. Therefore, one could apply the inverse process to obtain the parameters; that is, first decomposing the target sound using a filter bank, and then using the DFT to compute the parameters. This will, of course, yield a full set of parameters that will be N_F times larger than the actual signal, where N_F is the number of filters in the filterbank. To achieve some compression, one could retrieve only a number of parameters, let's say, the first N_P coefficients of the spectra of each subband.

Formally, these ideas are summarized in Algorithm 3.

Algorithm 2 The SubEnv Synth

Input: Let F be a filterbank, $N_F \in \mathbb{N}$ the number of filters in F , $S = \{S_1, \dots, S_{N_F}\}$ a (discrete) seed generated from white noise and F , $N_P \in \mathbb{N}$ the number of (complex) parameters to be used in each band, $P = (P_1, P_2, \dots, P_{N_F}) \in \mathcal{M}_{N_P, N_F}(\mathbb{C})$ the matrix (expressed by its columns) of parameters to generate the amplitude envelopes and $N \in \mathbb{N}$ the size of the discrete signal to be synthesized.

Output: A texture sound synthesized $y \in \mathbb{R}^N$.

- 1: Generate N_F spectra using the parameters in P in the following way:

$$A_j = ((P_j)_1, (P_j)_2, \dots, (P_j)_{N_P}, 0, \dots, 0, (\overline{P_j})_{N_P}, \dots, (\overline{P_j})_2) \in \mathbb{C}^N, \quad j = 1, \dots, N_F,$$

where \bar{z} correspond to the complex conjugate of $z \in \mathbb{C}$.

- 2: Use the spectra $\{A_j\}_{j=1}^{N_F}$ to generate N_F real signals using the Inverse Discrete Fourier Transform

$$a_j = \text{IDFT}(A_j) \in \mathbb{R}^N, \quad j = 1, \dots, N_F.$$

- 3: Impose the signals $\{a_j\}_{j=1}^{N_F}$ as amplitude envelopes on the seed to generate the bands

$$b_j = S_j \odot a_j, \quad j = 1, \dots, N_F,$$

where \odot represents the Hadamard (element-wise) product.

- 4: Combine the bands $\{b_j\}_{j=1}^{N_F}$ into a new signal

$$y[t] = \sum_{j=1}^{N_F} b_j[t], \quad t = 1, \dots, N.$$

- 5: **return** The synthesized signal y .
-

Algorithm 3 Parameter Extraction for the SubEnv Synth

Input: Let F be a filterbank, $N_F \in \mathbb{N}$ the number of filters in F , $N_P \in \mathbb{N}$ the number of (complex) parameters to be used in each band and $x \in \mathbb{R}^N$ the target texture sound to be resynthesized.

Output: A set of parameters to resynthesize x .

- 1: Generate a subband decomposition of x using F

$$F(x) = (x_1, \dots, x_{N_F}).$$

- 2: Compute the envelope of each band using the Hilbert transform

$$a_j = |H(x_j)|, \quad j = 1, \dots, N_F.$$

- 3: Compute the spectrum of each envelope subband using the Discrete Fourier Transform

$$A_j = \text{DFT}(a_j), \quad j = 1, \dots, N_F.$$

- 4: Take the first M coefficients of each spectrum

$$P_j = ((A_j)_0, (A_j)_1, \dots, (A_j)_{N_P}), \quad j = 1, \dots, N_F.$$

- 5: **return** The set of parameters $P = \{P_1, P_2, \dots, P_{N_F}\}$.
-

Some resynthesis examples using algorithms 2 and 3 can be found in Subsection 8.2.1.

3.1.3 Differentiability

One might be confused by the fact that the resulting signals are trigonometric polynomials, and hence, differentiability seems immediate. It is true that these signals, when considered as real functions, are differentiable (and even C^∞). However, when it comes to DDSF, one must ensure that the signal processor, as a whole, is a differentiable function with respect to its learnable parameters and its generated output.

To make it as clear as possible that the SubEnv Synth is, in fact, a differentiable signal processor, we shall decompose it as a composition of differentiable maps. To do so, we will write each step of Algorithm 2 as a simple function and then use that to directly compute all of its partial derivatives.

Step 1: First, let us define the complex matrices

$$\mathcal{C}_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & i & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & i & \cdots & 0 & 0 \\ & & & \ddots & & & \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 1 & i \end{pmatrix} \in \mathcal{M}_{N_F, 2N_P}(\mathbb{C}),$$

$$\mathcal{C}_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & 0 & 1 & -i \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 1 & -i & 0 & 0 \\ & & & \ddots & & & & & \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -i & \cdots & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \in \mathcal{M}_{N_F-1, 2N_P}(\mathbb{C}),$$

and let's concatenate them in the following way

$$\mathcal{C} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathcal{C}_1 \\ \mathbf{0}_{N-2N_F+1, 2N_P} \\ \mathcal{C}_2 \end{pmatrix} \in \mathcal{M}_{N, 2N_P}(\mathbb{C}),$$

where $\mathbf{0}_{N-2N_F+1, 2N_P}$ represents the zero matrix of $\mathcal{M}_{N-2N_F+1, 2N_P}(\mathbb{C})$.

Let $x_j, y_j \in \mathbb{R}$, $z_j = x_j + iy_j$ for $j = 1, \dots, N_P$, and note that the action of \mathcal{C} resembles step 1 of Algorithm 2 since

$$\mathcal{C} \begin{pmatrix} x_1 & y_1 & x_2 & y_2 & \cdots & x_{N_P} & y_{N_P} \end{pmatrix}^T = \begin{pmatrix} z_1 & \cdots & z_{N_P} & 0 & \cdots & 0 & z_{N_P} & \cdots & z_2 \end{pmatrix}^T. \quad (3.1)$$

In order to generalize this to the entire set of parameters let's note that, if N_P is the number of (complex) parameters per subband, then the space of parameters can be thought as $\mathcal{M}_{2N_P, N_F}(\mathbb{R})$, that is, an arbitrary element of the parameter space will be written as

$$P = \begin{pmatrix} P_1 & P_2 & \cdots & P_{N_F} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} x_{1,1} & x_{2,1} & \cdots & x_{N_F,1} \\ y_{1,1} & y_{2,1} & \cdots & y_{N_F,1} \\ & & \vdots & \\ x_{1,N_P} & x_{2,N_P} & \cdots & x_{N_F,N_P} \\ y_{1,N_P} & y_{2,N_P} & \cdots & y_{N_F,N_P} \end{pmatrix} \in \mathcal{M}_{2N_P, N_F}(\mathbb{R}).$$

It follows from (3.1) that the step 1 of the **SubEnv Synth** algorithm can be summarized by the simple equation

$$\mathcal{C}P = A = (A_1 \ A_2 \ \cdots \ A_{N_F}),$$

and in particular this step is both linear and differentiable, with partial derivatives given by

$$\frac{\partial A_j}{\partial P_k} = \delta(j-k) \cdot \mathcal{C}, \quad j, k = 1, \dots, N_F.$$

Step 2: In this step the IDFT is applied, so it can be summarized by the equation

$$\mathcal{F}^{-1}A = a = (a_1 \ a_2 \ \cdots \ a_{N_F}),$$

where $\mathcal{F} \in \mathcal{M}_N(\mathbb{C})$ correspond to the DFT matrix of size N . It follows that this step is also differentiable and its partial derivatives are given by

$$\frac{\partial a_j}{\partial A_k} = \delta(j - k) \cdot \mathcal{F}^{-1}, \quad j, k = 1, \dots, N_F.$$

Step 3: In this step the Hadamard product against the Seed is applied to generate the subbands, that is,

$$S \odot a = b = (b_1 \quad b_2 \quad \dots \quad b_{N_F}),$$

so it follows that its partial derivatives can be computed by

$$\frac{\partial b_j}{\partial a_k} = \delta(j - k) \cdot \text{diag}(S_j), \quad j, k = 1, \dots, N_F.$$

Step 4: Finally, the last step corresponds to horizontal sum of the matrix b , that is,

$$b \cdot (1 \quad 1 \quad \dots \quad 1)^T = y,$$

so it follows that

$$\frac{\partial y}{\partial b_j} = \text{Id}_N.$$

Remark 3.4 *It is important to note that, even though the partial derivatives computed in steps 1 and 2 may sometimes be complex numbers, this is not a problem. The entire algorithm corresponds to a real vector-valued function with respect to its parameters, so the chain rule will naturally eliminate the imaginary parts.*

3.2 P-VAE Synth: A synthesizer that captures Saint-Arnaud’s conception of a Texture Sound

As discussed in Section 2.1, a texture sound can be understood as the result of a combination of sound atoms and time transitions. While a time transition is relatively self-explanatory, a sound atom can be understood in various ways, and in any case, both concepts can be modeled in radically different ways. In this section, we introduce the Atom-Event Synth, a synthesizer inspired by the sound atom + time transition definition of a texture sound.

3.2.1 Formal Definition

Formally defining the P-VAE Synth requires three things: building the time transitions, generating atoms, and finally combining these two concepts. For clarity, these three aspects will be discussed separately.

About time

Given a set of time transitions between events, let's say $T_1, \dots, T_N \in \mathbb{R}^+$, one can always compute the signal of time stamps

$$E = \delta(T_1) + \delta(T_1 + T_2) + \dots + \delta\left(\sum_{j=1}^N T_j\right),$$

that is, a function of time that returns a 1 at every instant where an event is found, and a 0 otherwise.

Working with a signal of time stamps is beneficial for two reasons. First, it allows the computation of a big chunk of audio at once instead of one event at a time. And second, we can assign a value to each event by simple multiplication with a positive value in order to get amplitude information for each event, that is,

$$E = \alpha_1 \delta(T_1) + \alpha_2 \delta(T_1 + T_2) + \dots + \alpha_N \delta\left(\sum_{j=1}^N T_j\right).$$

This can be summarized in the following definition.

Definition 3.5 (Time-Stamped Signal) *Given an increasing sequence $0 < T_1 < T_2 < \dots < T_N$ and a sequence of values $\{\alpha_j\}_{j=1}^N \subset [0, 1]$, a signal of time stamps is defined as the tempered distribution*

$$E = \alpha_1 \delta(T_1) + \alpha_2 \delta(T_2) + \dots + \alpha_N \delta(T_N), \quad (3.2)$$

where $\delta(T)$ symbolizes the dirac delta tempered distribution defined by

$$\delta(T)(f) = f(T), \quad f \in \mathcal{S}(\mathbb{R}),$$

and $\mathcal{S}(\mathbb{R})$ represents the Schwartz class of functions.

Remark 3.6 *The importance of dealing with tempered distributions instead of simple functions is that we will use the time-stamped signal as a source for convolution. If we used simple functions, the convolution with a time-stamped signal of the form (3.2) would always return zero.*

Fortunately, there is no need to delve into theoretical matters here, since we are primarily interested in a discrete-time model. In this case, one can simply replace the Dirac deltas with their discrete counterparts, that is, canonical vectors (vectors in the canonical basis of \mathbb{R}^N).

Two dilemmas are intrinsic to this definition. First, it is too broad, so we need to find at least one method to generate this type of signal. Second, when dealing with audio synthesis, we will also have to handle concatenating frames of these types

of signals, which could create unexpected time transitions between the end of one frame and the beginning of another. Fortunately, these two problems can be solved using Poisson Processes.

In a Poisson Process, the time transitions are independent and identically distributed exponential random variables. A notable property of this distribution is that it is memoryless, which means that if $T \sim \text{Exp}(\lambda)$,

$$P(T > s + t \mid T > s) = P(T > t).$$

This means that the amount of time you have already waited for an event does not affect how much longer you will have to wait. In our context, this implies that we can easily generate a time-stamped signal using a Poisson Process. Because of the memoryless property, there is no need to worry about the time transitions generated by the concatenation of time-stamped signals.

In order to generate a discrete time-stamped signal from a Poisson Process with parameter λ , that is, with an average of λ events per second, one can condense the events happening during each bin of discrete time, that is, we will define the time-stamped signal E by

$$E[n] = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{at least one event occurred during the bin of time } n \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

In virtue of the memoryless property of the exponential distribution one can generate E one bin at a time by noting that

$$\begin{aligned} P(E[n] = 1) &= P(\text{at least one event occurred during the bin of time } n) \\ &= P(T < 1/f_s) \\ &= \int_0^{1/f_s} \lambda \exp(-\lambda t) dt \\ &= 1 - \exp\left(\frac{-\lambda}{f_s}\right), \end{aligned}$$

where $T \sim \text{Exp}(\lambda)$ and $f_s \in \mathbb{N}$ is the frequency sampling of the system.

It follows from the above that E can be fully characterized as a random vector where its entries are independent and identically distributed as $\text{Bern}(p)$, with $p = 1 - \exp(-\lambda/f_s)$.

Remark 3.7 *Observe that, since λ is the average number of events per second, one must expect $-\lambda/f_s \approx 0$. Thus, using the Taylor expansion of the exponential around 0, it follows that*

$$\begin{aligned} p &= 1 - \exp(-\lambda/f_s), \\ &\approx 1 - \left(1 - \frac{\lambda}{f_s}\right), \\ &= \frac{\lambda}{f_s}. \end{aligned}$$

This approximation reveals that, on average, a vector E computed as before will have λ events per second, so conserving this parameter will be essential for interpretation.

To sample E and generate a time-stamped signal usable in a deep learning environment, one must handle a stochastic layer that continuously samples from a Bernoulli distribution. This can be achieved, for example, using the Gumbel trick (see [Jang et al., 2016], [Maddison et al., 2016]), a discrete version of the reparameterization trick. However, since we are dealing only with a Bernoulli distribution, we can solve this by rewriting each Bernoulli-distributed value as a function of a Uniform distribution. More precisely, if $U \sim \text{Uniform}(0, 1)$, then

$$H(U - 1 + p) \sim \text{Bernoulli}(p), \quad (3.3)$$

where H is the Heaviside function. The importance of this equation is that it resembles the reparameterization trick by isolating the randomness in the random variable U in a way that it follows the required distribution and is differentiable with respect to the parameter p . This will be discussed further in Subsection 3.2.3.

A consequence of this is that one can easily sample E by sampling from a uniform distribution using equation (3.3). However, a time-stamped signal generated this way lacks depth, that is, it will have $\alpha_j = 1$ for all events. One way to address this, and what we will do, is to replace the Heaviside function H with one that allows more variability. Additionally, since this function will be processed by a neural network, it is beneficial to make it differentiable.

Let's define the family of differentiable *a.e.* functions $\Gamma = \{\gamma_{\alpha,p} \mid \alpha > 0, p \in (0, 1]\}$ by

$$\gamma_{\alpha,p}(x) = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{x}{p}\right)^\alpha, & x \geq 0 \\ 0, & x < 0 \end{cases}. \quad (3.4)$$

Now observe that $\gamma_{\alpha,p}(U - 1 + p)$ is a random variable that will be positive with probability p , so it retains the rate interpretation inherited from λ , but when positive, it will span random values in $[0, 1]$ with a distribution that depends on α . More precisely, let us denote $X_\alpha = \gamma_{\alpha,p}(U - 1 + p)$ and compute the probability density of $X_\alpha \mid X_\alpha > 0$. Note that $X_\alpha \mid X_\alpha > 0 \stackrel{d}{=} U^\alpha$, so applying the change of variables theorem, we get

$$\begin{aligned} f_{X_\alpha \mid X_\alpha > 0}(x) &= f_U(x^{1/\alpha})(x^{1/\alpha})' \\ &= \mathbb{1}_{(0,1)}(x^{1/\alpha}) \frac{x^{\frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha}}}{\alpha} \\ &= \alpha^{-1} x^{\frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha}} \mathbb{1}_{(0,1)}(x). \end{aligned}$$

Note that this density will favor $x = 1$ when $\alpha \approx 0$ and will favor $x = 0$ when $\alpha \gg 1$. In fact, one can prove that

$$\begin{aligned} U^\alpha &\xrightarrow{d} 1 \quad \text{as } \alpha \rightarrow 0, \text{ and} \\ U^\alpha &\xrightarrow{d} 0 \quad \text{as } \alpha \rightarrow \infty. \end{aligned}$$

Figure 3: Amplitude distribution of atoms, i.e., probability density of $X_\alpha \mid X_\alpha > 0$, with different parameters α .

Examples of the probability density of this distribution are shown in Figure 3.

As a result, deep time-stamped signals can be generated using two parameters: the rate of events per second and a parameter to control the distribution of the amplitudes of the events. This is summarized in Algorithm 4.

Algorithm 4 Time-Stamped Signal Generator

Input: Let $N \in \mathbb{N}$ be the target size, f_s the frequency sampling of the system, λ be the (average) rate of events per unit of time, and $\alpha > 1$ a parameter.

Output: A (discrete) time-stamped signal E .

- 1: Let $U_j \stackrel{\text{iid}}{\sim} \text{Uniform}(0, 1)$ and u_j be a realization of U_j for each $j = 1, \dots, N$.
- 2: Compute the vector $E \in \mathbb{R}^N$ defined by

$$E[j] = \gamma_{\alpha,p}(u_j - 1 + p), \quad j = 1, \dots, N,$$

where $p = 1 - \exp(-\lambda/f_s)$.

- 3: **return** The (discrete) time-stamped signal E .
-

About atoms

Atoms of sound, as described in the initial definitions of a texture sound, can essentially be anything. However, for each sound, one would expect all its atoms to be somewhat related. These relationships can be modeled in various ways, but in this work, we will conceptualize them probabilistically, that is, all atoms are drawn from the same distribution, or more precisely, they are independent realizations of the same stochastic process.

Knowing the probability distribution of our atoms does not imply that we must sample from it randomly to generate atoms. This actually could be problematic in a deep learning context. Instead, we seek a method to sample from this distribution in a differentiable manner.

As a result, our model requires the following components.

Definition 3.8 (Atom generator) *An atom generator is a triplet (A, \mathbb{Y}, F) such that:*

1. A is a stochastic process,
2. $\mathbb{Y} \subset \mathbb{R}^l$ is a (latent) space,
3. $F : \mathbb{Y} \rightarrow \Omega(A)$ is a differentiable function, where $\Omega(A)$ is the space of possible realizations of A .

There are many ways of generating this triplet. One which is particularly easy to get is using a Variational Auto-Encoder (VAE). More precisely, let's assume that we have a VAE with encoder $E : \mathbb{R}^M \rightarrow \mathbb{Y} \subset \mathbb{R}^l$, decoder $D : \mathbb{Y} \subset \mathbb{R}^l \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^M$, and that was trained on a dataset of target atoms of sounds of size M in such a way that the encoded dataset follow a distribution $N(0, \text{Id}_l)$. In such case, the triplet would be fully satisfied by taking the stochastic process $D(Z)$, where $Z \sim N(0, \text{Id}_N)$, \mathbb{Y} as the latent space; and D as the atom generator. This is summarized in the following proposition.

Proposition 3.9 *Given an already trained VAE with encoder E , latent space \mathbb{Y} and decoder D , the triplet $(D(Z), \mathbb{Y}, D)$ is an atom generator.*

The algorithm

Now that we know how to generate both time-stamped signals and atoms, the only thing remaining is to combine these two concepts in a way that is differentiable with respect to these signals.

Our goal is to use the time-stamped signal to capture the moments when an event occurs and place one atom of sound at each of these moments. One could achieve this by manually placing the atoms at the appropriate positions, but this approach is not differentiable. Fortunately, there is a straightforward solution to this problem: computing the convolution between the time-stamped signal and an atom. Specifically, the "sifting property" of the Dirac delta function states:

$$(\delta(t) * f)(s) = f(s - t),$$

which implies that convolving a time-stamped signal with an atom of sound will

Figure 4: Convolution between a delta acting as a time-stamped signal and an actual atom sound of water using the sifting property.

position the atom at each event, albeit in reverse (see Figure 4).

The only issue with using the previous approach is that directly implementing it will result in texture sounds composed of only one type of sound. However, a simple solution to this problem is to increase the rate of convolution: segment the time-stamped signal into a series of smaller segments, compute the convolution with a different atom of sound for each segment, and then overlap and add the results.

These ideas are summarized in Algorithm 5.

3.2.2 Parameter Extraction and Resynthesis

Due to the nature of the P-VAE `Synth`, it is not feasible to use this synthesizer without employing machine learning to train the VAE component. Moreover, the parameters λ and α , while corresponding to reasonably meaningful concepts in texture sounds, such as the rate of events and the distribution of amplitudes, are not straightforward to extract from a signal.

One might argue that, in some cases, such as texture sounds with very distinct atoms, one could estimate the rate of events per unit of time using onset detection functions. However, this approach is not universally applicable. For instance, how would you determine the rate of the sound of a river?

As a result, using the P-VAE `Synth` in a purely DSP environment to resynthesize a given texture sound can be quite challenging. Nevertheless, it remains possible to use it creatively to synthesize texture sounds by manually adjusting the parameters λ and α , provided that a VAE has been appropriately trained to generate sound atoms.

Algorithm 5 P-VAE Synthesizer

Input: Let $f_s \in \mathbb{N}$ be the frequency sampling of the system, $M \in \mathbb{N}$ be the size of each atom of sound, $N \in \mathbb{N}$ the length of the time-stamped signal and $K \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $K|N$ be the number of atoms. Let λ, α be parameters (as in Algorithm 4), $\mathbb{Y}, D : \mathbb{Y} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^M$ be the latent space and decoder of a VAE and $\{Y_j\}_{j=1}^K \subset \mathbb{Y}$ a sequence of encoded samples.

Output: A texture sound synthesized $y \in \mathbb{R}^{N+M-1}$.

- 1: Use the parameters f_s, λ, α, N to generate a time-stamped signal E using Algorithm 4.
- 2: Use the atom generator $(D(Z), \mathbb{Y}, D)$ (as in Proposition 3.9) to generate K atoms of sounds from the sequence $\{Y_j\}_{j=1}^K$, that is,

$$X_j = D(Y_j) \in \mathbb{R}^M, \quad j = 1, \dots, K.$$

- 3: Divide the time-stamped signal E into K frames of equal size $n = N/K$ without overlaps, that is,

$$E^{(j)} := (E_{(j-1)n}, E_{(j-1)n+1}, \dots, E_{jn}), \quad j = 1, \dots, K.$$

- 4: Compute the convolution between the atom of sound X_j and frames of time stamps $E^{(j)}$ to generate a snippet of sound

$$\tilde{s}_j = E^{(j)} * X_j \in \mathbb{R}^{n+M-1}.$$

- 5: Flip the snippets of sounds to fix the reverse atoms introduced by the sifting property (see Figure 4) by defining the snippets $\{s_j\}_{j=1}^K$ by

$$s_j[k] = \tilde{s}_j[n + M - 1 - k], \quad k = 1, \dots, K.$$

- 6: Initialize a signal $y = \vec{0} \in \mathbb{R}^{N+M-1}$ to apply the overlap and add algorithm using the snippets s_j with hop size equal to n .

7: **for** $j = 0, \dots, K - 1$ **do**

- 8: Overlap and add the signals s_j by

$$y[j \cdot n, j \cdot n + 1, \dots, (j + 1) \cdot n + M - 1]_+ = s_j$$

9: **end for**

10: **return** The synthesized signal y .

3.2.3 Differentiability

As with the `SubEnv Synth`, we are interested in using the `P-VAE Synth` in a DDSP-based architecture, so it is important that this signal processor is differentiable.

Similarly to subsection 3.1.3, we will discuss the differentiability of each step in Algorithm 5 to fully understand the synthesizer. The differentiability of the entire synthesizer will then follow, as it is a composition of differentiable functions.

Step 1: In this step, the time-stamped signal is generated using Algorithm 4. This algorithm is designed to ensure that the result is differentiable with respect to its parameters, λ and α .

To demonstrate that this step is indeed differentiable with respect to its parameters, it is important to understand that, similar to the classical Reparametrization Trick (see [Kingma and Welling, 2013]), randomness is removed from the forward pass by using an auxiliary variable—in this case, the set of auxiliary random variables U_j defined in Algorithm 4. The output of this algorithm is a vector $E \in \mathbb{R}^N$ such that

$$E[j] = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{u_j - \exp(-\lambda/f_s)}{1 - \exp(-\lambda/f_s)} \right)^\alpha, & \tilde{u}_j \geq 0 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad (3.5)$$

where $\tilde{u}_j = u_j - \exp(-\lambda/f_s)$ is defined for the sake of order.

It follows that its partial derivatives are

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial E[j]}{\partial \alpha} &= \begin{cases} \left(\frac{u_j - \exp(-\lambda/f_s)}{1 - \exp(-\lambda/f_s)} \right)^\alpha \ln \left(\frac{u_j - \exp(-\lambda/f_s)}{1 - \exp(-\lambda/f_s)} \right), & \tilde{u}_j \geq 0 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\ \frac{\partial E[j]}{\partial \lambda} &= \begin{cases} -\alpha \frac{(u_j - 1) \exp(\lambda/f_s)}{f_s (\exp(\lambda/f_s) - 1)^2} \left(\frac{u_j - \exp(-\lambda/f_s)}{1 - \exp(-\lambda/f_s)} \right)^{\alpha-1}, & \tilde{u}_j \geq 0 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

Step 2: In the second step of Algorithm 5 a set of atoms are generated using the decoder of an already trained VAE, so this step will be differentiable as long as such decoder is. This is typically a default property of decoders, since they are designed to be able to train efficiently.

Step 3: In this step, the time-stamped signal is segmented in K sub-segments of size $n = N/K$. This process is actually linear since

$$I_j E = E^{(j)},$$

where $I_j \in \mathcal{M}_{n,N}(\mathbb{R})$ is defined by

$$I_j = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{n,j-n} & \text{Id}_n & \mathbf{0}_{n,N-(j+1)n} \end{pmatrix},$$

where $\mathbf{0}_{a,b}$ represents the zero matrix in $\mathcal{M}_{a,b}(\mathbb{R})$.

It follows that this step is differentiable and that its partial derivatives correspond with

$$\frac{\partial E^{(j)}}{\partial E} = I_j.$$

Steps 4, 5, 6 and 7: The last steps correspond to convolution, flipping and the overlap and add algorithm, all of which are fairly well known to be differentiable.

Chapter 4

Loss Function

In this chapter, we discuss the need for a new loss function tailored specifically for texture sounds. This discussion leads to identifying a series of desirable properties for such a loss function. We then define a loss function inspired by these properties and the work of McDermott and Simoncelli [McDermott et al., 2009], [McDermott and Simoncelli, 2011] and [McDermott et al., 2013].

4.1 Designing a Loss Function Specifically for Texture Sounds

In their original work, Engel et al. used a multiscale spectrogram loss function. This choice is particularly suitable for their task, which involved synthesizing violin sounds in relatively small frames of audio with only two inputs: pitch and loudness. The effectiveness of this loss function in this context lies in the model's objective to perfectly synthesize the violin sound at every moment in time.

However, this approach presents various issues when applied to texture sounds. First, it is important to note that pitch is not a particularly informative feature for texture sounds. Therefore, it is crucial to determine which features should be used in the encoding process (further discussed in Chapter 5). Even with an appropriate set of features, it is not necessary for two texture sounds to have identical magnitude spectra at every moment in time for them to sound the same. Julesz proposed the "Julesz Conjecture" in this regard, and McDermott and Simoncelli empirically refined it, suggesting that the multiscale spectrogram loss function is too restrictive for texture sounds.

In the following paragraphs, we will qualitatively and philosophically explore the properties that a well-designed loss function for texture sounds should have to respect both their stochastic nature and our current understanding of them.

Overall Structure Focus: The stochastic nature of texture sounds means that they sound unpredictable and similar to filtered noise when heard over short periods of time. However, over longer periods, they are easily recognizable and stable. Thus, a loss function designed for texture sounds should focus on computations over large audio frames, emphasizing the overall structure of the sound rather than its instantaneous and local details.

Time Invariance: Due to their stochastic nature, texture sounds can be chopped and rearranged with minimal noticeable difference in their perceived sound. This is not true for most types of sounds; for instance, chopping and rearranging a violin recording will introduce artifacts at each chop and most importantly disrupt any melody. Therefore, a loss function for texture sounds must exhibit some degree of time invariance.

Respect for Stochastic Nature: Both Julesz and Rosenthal suggest that a texture sound results from a random process on at least two levels: events in time and timbre. A loss function capturing these properties should be able to recognize that two fire sounds recorded in the same place but at different times are the same sound, and thus the loss between them should be zero. Although such a loss function may not be practically feasible, the goal is to approximate this ideal. According to Julesz’s conjecture, and McDermott and Simoncelli’s synthesis approach, the stochastic nature of textures can be understood through direct comparison of their statistics. Thus, a well-designed loss function for texture sounds should incorporate some degree of statistical invariance.

4.2 TextStat: A Loss Function Inspired by the Work of McDermott and Simoncelli

As discussed in Subsection 2.2.2, McDermott and Simoncelli empirically demonstrated that synthesizing certain types of texture sounds can be effectively achieved by imposing a set of statistical constraints. An important implication of this finding is that these statistics can serve as a new representation for comparing texture sounds. In this section, we introduce the `TextStat` loss function, inspired by this idea. Rather than computing a direct distance between two signals, `TextStat` compares their statistical representations.

The `TextStat` loss function satisfies the properties mentioned in the previous section for the following reasons:

Overall Structure Focus: Statistics describe the overall structure of a signal. As long as these statistics are computed on sufficiently large frames of audio and are not overly complex, this loss function aligns with the focus on overall structure.

Time Invariance: The statistics used in the `TextStat` loss function focus on the distribution of signal values, without considering time. This inherently makes the function time-invariant.

Respect for the Stochastic Nature: Assuming that texture sounds behave stochastically, the best approach to capture their behavior is by treating them as random variables or, more precisely, stochastic processes. In this context, understanding their probabilistic behavior relies on statistical analysis.

To precisely define the new loss function, we need to accurately describe the set of statistics used. In what remains of this section, five sets of statistics will be defined and combined to form the `TextStat` loss function. While these sets will closely resemble those discussed in Subsection 2.2.2, some modifications have been made for scalability and comparability. Therefore, it is important to detail these main changes.

Preprocessing

As in McDermott and Simoncelli’s work, the computation of statistics is performed not directly on the signal but on the envelopes obtained from a subband decomposition of the signal. They found that subband decompositions yield better results when the parameters are derived from biologically plausible filterbanks. Therefore, in this case, the subband decomposition is achieved using an Equivalent Rectangular Bandwidth (ERB) filterbank. This filterbank is designed with central frequencies distributed according to the ERB model (see [Glasberg and Moore, 1990]) and ensures that the summed squared frequency response of the filterbank remains constant across the frequency domain (including a low-pass and a high-pass filter). Empirical results (see Section 8.2) have demonstrated that for various types of texture sounds, it is beneficial to adjust the frequency domain resolution of the decomposition, which can be achieved by increasing the size of the filterbank.

Assuming the filterbank has been designed with the properties described and consists of N_F filters, let us denote it as $F = \{f_j\}_{j=1}^{N_F}$. The subband decomposition of a target signal x is then computed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} F(x) &= (f_1 * x, f_2 * x, \dots, f_{N_F} * x) \\ &= (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_{N_F}). \end{aligned} \tag{4.1}$$

Subbands y_1, y_2, \dots, y_{N_F} are bandlimited versions of the original signal, the envelopes of which are computed using the Hilbert transform

$$\tilde{e}_j = |H_j(y_j)|,$$

and are further processed through a compressive nonlinearity¹

$$e_j = \text{pow}(\tilde{e}_j, 0.3), \quad j = 1, \dots, N_F.$$

This process yield a series of compressed envelopes, from which we will compute the first two sets of statistics.

¹The specific function was taken directly from the code implementation of McDermott and Simoncelli’s work.

Statistic set 1

The first set of statistics correspond to the computation of the first four normalized moments, that is,

$$\begin{aligned}
 M_1^j &= \frac{\mathbb{E}(e_j)}{\mu_j} = \frac{\mu_j}{\mu_j} \\
 M_2^j &= \frac{\mathbb{E}((e_j - \mu_j)^2)}{\mu_j^2} = \frac{\sigma_j^2}{\mu_j^2} \\
 M_3^j &= \frac{\mathbb{E}((e_j - \mu_j)^3)}{\sigma_j^3} \\
 M_4^j &= \frac{\mathbb{E}((e_j - \mu_j)^4)}{\sigma_j^4}
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.2}$$

for $j = 1, \dots, N_F$. Then these statistics are saved in the matrix $\mathcal{S}_1 \in \mathcal{M}_{N_F, 4}(\mathbb{R})$ defined by

$$(\mathcal{S}_1)_{j,k} = M_k^j, \tag{4.3}$$

for $j = 1, \dots, N_F$ and $k = 1, \dots, 4$.

Statistics set 2

The second set of statistics consist of cross-band (Pearson) correlations, that is,

$$\begin{aligned}
 C_{j,k} &= \frac{\rho(e_j, e_k)}{\sigma_j \sigma_k} \\
 &= \frac{\mathbb{E}((e_j - \mu_j)(e_k - \mu_k))}{\sigma_j \sigma_k},
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.4}$$

for $j, k = 1, \dots, N_F$.

As in the previous case, all these statistics are then saved in the matrix $\mathcal{S}_2 \in \mathcal{M}_{N_F}(\mathbb{R})$ defined by

$$(\mathcal{S}_2)_{j,k} = C_{j,k}, \quad j, k = 1, \dots, N_F. \tag{4.5}$$

Further processing

Before computing the following three sets of statistics, it is necessary to further process the compressed envelopes $\{e_j\}_{j=1}^{N_F}$. To do this, we will once again follow the approach of McDermott and Simoncelli. First, each subband e_j is further decomposed using a modulation filterbank. Modulation filterbanks are a standard tool for modeling auditory processing of amplitude modulation (see, for example, [Fassel and Pueschel, 1993] and [Dau et al., 1997]) and can be implemented in various ways. For this work, we have chosen to use a modulation filterbank with center frequencies distributed logarithmically, as in [Dau et al., 1997]. This filterbank is designed so that the summed squared frequency response remains constant across the frequency domain (when including a low-pass and a high-pass filter) and has a fixed size of six.

Note that, while the number of filters in the cochlear filterbank is variable, the number of filters in the modulation filterbank is fixed. This choice is based on two

considerations. First, the signals being analyzed are relatively simple, as they correspond to envelopes of subbands; thus, a broad decomposition generally captures more than enough information. Second, increasing the size of the modulation filterbank would significantly increase the computational cost of calculating the next three sets of statistics, so we have capped the number for optimization purposes.

Let $G = \{g_j\}_{j=1}^6$ denote the modulation filterbank and the modulation bands of the envelope subbands e_j be given by

$$\begin{aligned} G(e_j) &= (g_1 * e_j, g_2 * e_j, \dots, g_6 * e_j) \\ &= (m_{j,1}, m_{j,2}, \dots, m_{j,6}), \end{aligned} \quad (4.6)$$

for $j = 1, \dots, N_F$.

This process yields a series of modulation bands, from which we will compute the last three sets of statistics.

Statistic set 3

The third set of statistics corresponds, roughly, to the proportion of energy in each modulation band. More precisely, let's define the matrix $\mathcal{S}_3 \in \mathcal{M}_{N,6}$ by

$$(\mathcal{S}_3)_{j,k} = \frac{\sigma_{j,k}}{\sigma_j}, \quad (4.7)$$

for $j = 1, \dots, N_F$ and $k = 1, \dots, 6$, where

$$\sigma_{j,k} = \sqrt{\mathbb{E}(m_{j,k}^2) - \mathbb{E}(m_{j,k})^2},$$

are the standard deviances for each modulation band.

Statistic set 4

The fourth set of statistics corresponds to the Pearson correlations between modulation bands corresponding to the same envelope subband. More precisely let's define the matrix $\mathcal{S}_4 \in \mathcal{M}_{N,15}$ with j -th row defined as the 15-dimensional vector

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathcal{S}_4)_j = (& \rho_{1,2}^j \quad \rho_{1,3}^j \quad \rho_{1,4}^j \quad \rho_{1,5}^j \quad \rho_{1,6}^j \quad \rho_{2,3}^j \quad \rho_{2,4}^j \quad \dots \\ & \dots \quad \rho_{2,5}^j \quad \rho_{2,6}^j \quad \rho_{3,4}^j \quad \rho_{3,5}^j \quad \rho_{3,6}^j \quad \rho_{4,5}^j \quad \rho_{4,6}^j \quad \rho_{5,6}^j), \end{aligned} \quad (4.8)$$

where

$$\rho_{k,l}^j = \rho(m_{j,k}, m_{j,l}),$$

for $j = 1, \dots, N_F$ and $k, l = 1, \dots, 6$.

Statistic set 5

The last set of statistics corresponds to the Pearson correlations between modulation bands corresponding to the same frequency band but different envelope subband.

More precisely let T_n be the n -th triangular number, that is,

$$T_n = \sum_{j=1}^n j,$$

and let's define the matrix $\mathcal{S}_5 \in \mathcal{M}_{6, T_{N_F-1}}(\mathbb{R})$ such that its j -th row is the vector in T_{N_F-1} -dimensions

$$(\mathcal{S}_5)_j = (\tilde{\rho}_{1,2}^j \quad \cdots \quad \tilde{\rho}_{1,N_F}^j \quad \tilde{\rho}_{2,3}^j \quad \cdots \quad \tilde{\rho}_{2,N_F}^j \quad \cdots \quad \tilde{\rho}_{N_F-1,N_F}^j) \quad (4.9)$$

where

$$\tilde{\rho}_{k,l}^j = \rho(m_{k,j}, m_{l,j}),$$

for $j = 1, \dots, 6$ and $k, l = 1, \dots, N_F$.

The loss function

Now that we have the five sets of statistics well-defined, we can finally define the `TextStat` loss function.

Definition 4.1 (TextStat loss function) *The TextStat loss function is defined as*

$$\mathcal{L}_{\alpha,\beta}(x, y) = \exp\left(\frac{1}{\beta} \left(\sum_{j=1}^5 \alpha_j \cdot \|\mathcal{S}_j(x) - \mathcal{S}_j(y)\|_2\right) - 1\right),$$

where $\alpha = (\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_5) \in (\mathbb{R}^+)^5$, $\beta \in \mathbb{R}^+$ are parameters, x, y are a pair of signals of equal length, and $\mathcal{S}_1(x), \mathcal{S}_2(y), \dots, \mathcal{S}_5(y)$ are their matrices of statistics computed as in (4.3), (4.5), (4.7), (4.8), and (4.9).

Remark 4.2 *Note that the parameters α and β do not impose any strong constraints on the loss function; however, it is important to set these parameters appropriately for optimal training.*

The parameter α is used to weight the different types of statistics correctly. Meanwhile, the parameter β sets a threshold for the expression

$$\sum_{j=1}^5 \alpha_j \cdot \|\mathcal{S}_j(x) - \mathcal{S}_j(y)\|_2,$$

such that when this expression exceeds β , the training curve becomes dramatically steeper. In contrast, for values below β , the slope of the loss function is less steep. By setting β appropriately, we can also interpret the values given by the loss function: a loss under 1 indicates that the signals are very similar in terms of their statistics.

Chapter 5

Encoders and Decoders

The DDSF architecture, as described in the original paper [Engel et al., 2020], resembles an autoencoder in that an initial layer of encoders transforms the input signal into a series of meaningful features, which are then passed through a standard decoder and a signal processor to recreate the signal itself. This chapter discusses the need to modify the original encoders. Following that, the specific encoders and decoders used in this work are also discussed.

5.1 What is wrong with the encoders in the original DDSF paper?

In short, there is nothing inherently wrong with any of the encoders. However, the effectiveness of an encoder for a particular task depends heavily on the nature of that task.

In the original DDSF architecture, the encoders used in the violin synthesizer model correspond to pitch and loudness. More precisely, pitch is computed using a pre-trained model known as CREPE, introduced in [Kim et al., 2018], and loudness is computed using A-weightings as described in [Hantrakul et al., 2019]. These features were chosen for the following reasons.

1. *These features are particularly meaningful when synthesizing a violin:* Given only pitch and loudness, and considering that the signal processor used is the Harmonic + Stochastic model discussed in 2.2, the model only needs to learn how to map these features onto the amplitude distribution of harmonics, which is a reasonable task.
2. *These features can be used to drive the model in a meaningful way:* It is reasonable to consider using these parameters to control the synthesis process. In fact, this is what led the authors to introduce this model as one that, in certain cases, can solve the task of timbre transfer.

The main issue here is that neither of these arguments holds for Texture Sounds. Pitch and loudness are not meaningful enough to either synthesize a texture sound from scratch or control the synthesis in a reasonable way. The real question, then, is: What are some meaningful features for a Texture Sound?

5.2 What are some meaningful features for a Texture Sound?

As discussed in 2.1, Texture Sounds encompass a vast range of sounds, including wind, rain, engines, insects, bubbling, and more. Given the immense variety within this category, identifying universal and meaningful features becomes a challenging task.

To be precise, it is important to understand what makes a feature meaningful. This problem can be approached from various perspectives, but one particularly relevant to this work involves focusing on the features that naturally emerge when we consider how organisms perceive and interact with their environments. This perspective is known as the Ecological Approach to Auditory Event Perception, and a framework for studying perception from this angle was introduced by William W. Gaver in a series of articles [Gaver, 1993a], [Gaver, 1993b].

Specifically, in [Gaver, 1993b], Gaver introduces a framework to account for what he describes as “ecologically relevant perceptual entities”—dimensions and features of events that we actually perceive through listening. By doing this, Gaver seeks to answer the question, “What do we hear?” He does so by briefly considering the range of information about the world that we hear, and then providing a specific list of types of events and their corresponding audible attributes (see Figure 5).

Gaver’s ecological approach to auditory events might seem complex and convoluted, but it clearly illustrates how challenging it is to find a meaningful set of features for Texture Sounds.

Although Gaver’s ecological approach is insightful, it is evident that most of the audible attributes mentioned in Figure 5 correspond primarily to the physical properties of the objects involved in sound generation. These features are ideal, but to use them, one would need either to design a function that computes these features from a sound or to have a well-annotated dataset. Unfortunately, both cases fall outside the scope of this thesis.

A workaround is to use features that, while not as semantically meaningful as the ones described earlier, can be accurately computed using DSP. In this context, and since the work in this thesis aims to build a framework capable of generating multiple types of Texture Sounds, three multi-purpose feature extractors were implemented so that the model can be driven and controlled by meaningful parameters. These features listed below.

Figure 5: Map of everyday sounds, including their type and audible attributes. Figure taken from [Gaver, 1993b].

1. *Spectral Centroid*: The mean of the magnitude spectrum can be thought of as an analog to pitch in the context of Texture Sounds. However, it is undoubtedly not as meaningful as its counterpart in the context of synthesizing pitched instruments.
2. *Spectral Deviation*: The mean of the magnitude spectrum lacks strong meaning on its own. However, when higher-order moments are considered, it can become much more effective as a general descriptor of a texture sound. Therefore, the second multi-purpose feature implemented was the standard deviation of the magnitude spectrum.
3. *Rate*: Rate is not a standard feature and can have different meanings in various contexts. However, we have observed that some onset detection algorithms (such as those in `librosa.onset` from [McFee et al., 2024]) perform well in counting events for certain texture sounds. For this reason, a differentiable event count-type feature was also implemented in this work.

5.3 The encoder

Only one type of encoder was implemented in this thesis, however, it has many parameters to make it appropriate for each model. This encoder is slightly different from the one described in the original DDSP paper [Engel et al., 2020], but it closely follows the implementation in the PyTorch version of the DDSP architecture developed at IRCAM, which is publicly available on github.com/acids-ircam/ddsp_pytorch.

Figure 6: MLP module.

The encoder architecture proposed here uses a specific type of Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP). This MLP consists of a feedforward neural network with d layers, each of which includes a linear transformation followed by layer normalization and a Leaky ReLU activation function. All hidden layers have a uniform size of $h_s \in \mathbb{N}$. From now on, the application of this MLP to a signal x will be denoted by

$$\text{MLP}(x \mid h_s, d, \theta) = X \in \mathbb{R}^{h_s}, \quad (5.1)$$

where θ corresponds to the set of (learnable) hyperparameters of the MLP. For a graphical representation of the MLP module see Figure 6. The encoder’s input consists of two real numbers corresponding to two preselected features from those discussed in the previous section, precomputed for each audio frame of size $N \in \mathbb{N}$. Let’s denote these features as (f_1, f_2) . These features are expanded through an MLP as defined in equation (5.1), with hidden size, depth, and hyperparameters set to h_s , $d \in \mathbb{N}$, and θ_1, θ_2 , respectively. Specifically, we have

$$F_j = \text{MLP}(f_j \mid h_s, d, \theta_j) \in \mathbb{R}^{h_s}, \quad j = 1, 2. \quad (5.2)$$

As in IRCAM’s implementation, these two expanded features are then used to compute a third latent variable using a single-layer Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) of size h_s with hyperparameters θ , that is,

$$Z = \text{GRU}(F_1, F_2 \mid \theta) \in \mathbb{R}^{h_s}. \quad (5.3)$$

Finally, these three variables are concatenated into the latent vector

$$L = (F_1, F_2, Z) \in \mathbb{R}^{3h_s}. \quad (5.4)$$

The following definition summarizes this process.

Definition 5.1 (DDSP-Encoder) *Let $h_s, d \in \mathbb{N}$ be the hidden size and depth parameters. The DDSP-Encoder is defined as the function $\text{enc} : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{3h_s}$ such that*

$$\text{enc}(f_1, f_2) = L,$$

where L is computed following equations (5.2), (5.3), and (5.4). For a visual repre-

Figure 7: The DDSF-Encoder layer.

resentation of the encoder function, see Figure 7.

Remark 5.2 The DDSF-Encoder function maps the input feature vector (f_1, f_2) to the latent representation $L \in \mathbb{R}^{3h_s}$, with its (learnable) hyperparameters being θ_1, θ_2 , and θ , corresponding to the two MLPs and the GRU.

5.4 Decoders

The decoders implemented in this thesis closely resemble the original ones, except they are adjusted to output parameters specific to the signal processors introduced in this thesis. Since two signal processors were defined in Chapter 3, this naturally implies the need for two types of decoders.

5.4.1 The DDSF-decoder: a decoder compatible with the SubEnv Synth

A decoder compatible with the SubEnv Synth must take the latent representation L as input and output the set of complex parameters required by the synthesizer. To achieve this, the decoder is composed of an amplitude decoder and an angle decoder. These two decoders take the same input L and apply an independent MLP, as defined in (5.1), with hidden size, depth, and hyperparameters given by h_s , d , and θ_ρ , θ_φ respectively. The output is further processed by a Linear layer

that outputs real vectors of size $N_F \cdot N_P$, where N_F is the number of filters in the filterbank used by the synthesizer, and N_P is the number of parameters to generate each band (see 2). More precisely,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{dec}_\rho(L) &= A \cdot \text{MLP}(L \mid h_s, d, \theta_\rho) \\ \text{dec}_\varphi(L) &= B \cdot \text{MLP}(L \mid h_s, d, \theta_\varphi), \end{aligned} \quad (5.5)$$

where $A, B \in \mathcal{M}_{h_s, N_F \cdot N_P}$ are learnable matrices corresponding to the linear layer.

Next, these sets of amplitudes and phases are mapped to the intervals $[0, 1]$ and $[0, 2\pi]$ using sigmoids, and then combined into complex parameters using a polar-to-Cartesian transformation. This can be summarized by the equations

$$\begin{aligned} \rho &= \sigma(\text{dec}_\rho(L)) \\ \varphi &= 2\pi\sigma(\text{dec}_\varphi(L)), \end{aligned} \quad (5.6)$$

and the vector of parameters $p \in \mathbb{C}^{N_F \cdot N_P}$ defined by

$$p_j = \rho_j \cos(\varphi_j) + i\rho_j \sin(\varphi_j), \quad j = 1, \dots, N_F \cdot N_P. \quad (5.7)$$

Finally, the actual set of complex parameter vectors can be obtained by simple segmentation of p , that is,

$$P_j = (p_{(j-1) \cdot N_P}, p_{(j-1) \cdot N_P + 1}, \dots, p_{j \cdot N_P - 1}), \quad j = 1, \dots, N_F. \quad (5.8)$$

The following definition summarizes this process.

Definition 5.3 (DDSP-Decoder) *Let $h_s, d, N_F, N_P \in \mathbb{N}$ be the hidden size, depth, number of filters, and number of parameters per envelope. The DDSP-Decoder is defined as the function $\text{dec} : \mathbb{R}^{3h_s} \rightarrow \mathcal{M}_{N_P, N_F}(\mathbb{C})$ given by*

$$\text{dec}(L) = (P_1, P_2, \dots, P_{N_F}), \quad (5.9)$$

where the vectors $P_j \in \mathbb{C}^{N_P}$ are computed by following equations (5.5), (5.6), (5.7), and (5.8). For a visual representation of the decoder function, see Figure 8.

Remark 5.4 *The DDSP-Decoder function takes the latent vector L and outputs the set of (complex) parameters P to be used by the `SubEnv Synth`. Its (learnable) hyperparameters correspond to θ_ρ , θ_φ , A , and B , corresponding to the two MLPs and the two additional linear layers.*

5.4.2 The Stochastic DDSP-Decoder: A Decoder Compatible with the P-VAE Synth

A decoder compatible with the P-VAE Synth must take the latent representation L as input and output two types of parameters: the time-related parameters λ, α , and

Figure 8: The DDSF-Decoder layer.

the atom generation-related parameters $\{Y_j\}_j \subset \mathbb{Y}$ (see Algorithm 5 for reference). To accomplish this, the decoder consists of a time decoder and an atom decoder. These two decoders take the same input L and apply independent MLPs, as defined in (5.1), with hidden size, depth, and hyperparameters given by h_s , d , θ_t , and θ_a , respectively. The output is then processed by a Linear layer that outputs vectors with the target sizes

$$\begin{aligned} \text{dec}_t(L) &= A \cdot \text{MLP}(L \mid h_s, d, \theta_t) \\ \text{dec}_a(L) &= B \cdot \text{MLP}(L \mid h_s, d, \theta_a), \end{aligned} \quad (5.10)$$

where $A \in \mathcal{M}_{h_s, 2}(\mathbb{R})$ and $B \in \mathcal{M}_{h_s, Kl}(\mathbb{R})$, with $l = \dim(\mathbb{Y})$ and $K = M/N$ as defined in Algorithm 5.

For the time parameters, we require $\lambda, \alpha > 0$, so they are computed using the time decoder followed by the activation layer:

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda &= \text{ReLu}(\text{dec}_t(L)_0), \\ \alpha &= \text{ReLu}(\text{dec}_t(L)_1) \end{aligned} \quad (5.11)$$

Finally, the encoded parameters $\{Y_j\}_{j=1}^K$ can be retrieved from the atom decoder using simple segmentation:

$$Y_j = (\text{dec}_a(L)_{(j-1)M}, \text{dec}_a(L)_{(j-1)M+1}, \dots, \text{dec}_a(L)_{jM-1}), \quad j = 1, \dots, K. \quad (5.12)$$

The following definition summarizes this process.

Definition 5.5 (Stochastic DDSF-Decoder) *Let $h_s, d \in \mathbb{N}$ be the hidden size and depth parameters, $K = M/N \in \mathbb{N}$ as in Algorithm 5, and $l = \dim(\mathbb{Y})$ the dimension of the latent space of the VAE to be used. The Stochastic DDSF-Decoder is defined as the function $\text{dec}_s : \mathbb{R}^{3h_s} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathcal{M}_{l, K}(\mathbb{R})$ given by*

$$\text{dec}_s(L) = ((\lambda, \alpha), (Y_1, Y_2, \dots, Y_K)), \quad (5.13)$$

where λ, α and $\{Y_j\}_{j=1}^K \subset \mathbb{Y}$ are computed by following equations (5.10), (5.11), and

Figure 9: The Stochastic DDSF-Decoder layer.

(5.12). For a visual representation of the decoder function, see Figure 9.

Remark 5.6 The name "Stochastic DDSF-Decoder" is derived from its connection to the P-VAE Synth, which is a stochastic signal processor. However, there is nothing inherently stochastic about the Stochastic DDSF-Decoder itself. It takes the latent vector L and outputs the set of parameters λ, α and $Y = \{Y_j\}_{j=1}^K$ to be used by the P-VAE Synth. Its (learnable) hyperparameters correspond to θ_t, θ_a, A , and B , associated with the two MLPs and the two additional linear layers.

Chapter 6

Architectures

In this chapter, two neural network architectures are proposed based on the signal processor, loss function, and encoders discussed in Chapters 3, 4, and 5, respectively. First, we discuss a direct implementation of the DDSP architecture using the **SubEnv Synth**. Then, we address an implementation using the **P-VAE Synth**, which includes a stochastic layer and is thus discussed separately to emphasize the challenges associated with training it.

6.1 Differentiable Digital Signal Processing

The DDSP autoencoder architecture, as originally proposed in [Engel et al., 2020] and discussed in 2.3.2, comprises three components. The two fundamental components of any autoencoder are the encoder and the decoder. In DDSP, the output of the decoder is fed into a signal processor, which is a differentiable layer capable of synthesizing sounds from a set of parameters. Although the model presented here follows the same general structure, we will detail each component.

Model Parameters: For the model to function correctly, certain parameters are necessary. First, although the model’s input is a vector of features, it must know the size of the target sound to synthesize, denoted as $N \in \mathbb{N}$. Second, multiple MLPs as described in (5.1) are employed, all sharing the same hidden size, $h_s \in \mathbb{N}$, and depth $d \in \mathbb{N}$. Third, the signal processing aspect of the model is powered by the **SubEnv Synth**, which requires a seed (see Definition 3.1) S generated from a fixed filterbank comprising N_F filters, along with the number of (complex) parameters, $N_P \in \mathbb{N}$, that the synthesizer uses to control each subband.

Encoder: The encoder utilized in this model is defined by Definition 5.1 with parameters h_s and d . It produces the latent representation of the signal, denoted as $L = \text{enc}(f_1, f_2)$, where (f_1, f_2) represents the input feature vector.

Decoder: The decoder employed in this model is defined by Definition 5.3 with parameters h_s , d , N_F , and N_P . It generates the set of parameters required by the

Figure 10: The DDSP architecture.

signal processor to synthesize a signal, denoted as $P = \text{dec}(L)$, where L is the latent representation.

Signal Processor: The signal processor used is the `SubEnv Synth` with a fixed seed S . This processor takes the parameter set P and outputs the synthesized signal.

By combining these components, we obtain a neural network architecture that mirrors the original DDSP design but is specifically adapted for synthesizing texture sounds. A visual representation of this architecture is shown in Figure 10.

6.2 Stochastic Differentiable Digital Signal Processing

The model described in this section is analogous to the one presented in the previous section. It utilizes the same encoder but employs a different approach to achieve the same task. Here, we detail the model parameters, decoder, and signal processor.

Model Parameters: For the model to function correctly, it must be aware of certain parameters. First, although the input to the architecture is a vector of features, the model needs to know the size of the target sound to synthesize, denoted as $N \in \mathbb{N}$. Second, multiple MLPs, as described in (5.1), are used, all sharing the same hidden size, $h_s \in \mathbb{N}$, and depth $d \in \mathbb{N}$. Third, the signal processing component of this model is powered by the `P-VAE Synth`, which requires the components of a pre-trained VAE, denoted as \mathbb{Y} and D , as described in Algorithm 5.

Decoder: The decoder used in this model is defined by Definition 5.5, with parameters h_s , d , \mathbb{Y} , and $K = M/N$. It produces the set of parameters needed by the signal processor to generate a signal, denoted as $((\lambda, \alpha), (Y_1, Y_2, \dots, Y_K)) = \text{dec}_s(L)$, where L represents the latent representation.

Figure 11: The stochastic DDSP architecture.

Signal Processor: The signal processor used is the P-VAE Synth. This processor takes the parameter set $((\lambda, \alpha), (Y_1, Y_2, \dots, Y_K))$ and generates the output signal.

Combining these components results in a neural network architecture that mirrors the original DDSP structure but is specifically tailored for synthesizing texture sounds. A visual representation of this architecture is shown in Figure 11.

Remark 6.1 *The term "stochastic" in this architecture refers to the inclusion of a random component within the signal processor. As discussed in Subsection 3.2.3, this signal processor is designed to be differentiable with respect to its parameters, despite its inherent randomness, similar to the classical reparameterization trick. For a visual comparison between the forward passes of a VAE trained using the reparameterization trick and the generation of time-stamped signals, see Figure 12.*

Figure 12: Comparison of stochastic forward passes. On the left is the classical reparameterization trick. On the right is the time-stamped signal generator. The former manages randomness using the random vector Z , while the latter does so using the random vector U .

Chapter 7

Creative Applications

In this chapter, we provide a brief overview of some applications of the models presented in this thesis. First, we discuss how to use and control these models in real-time. Then, we highlight what may be the most well-known application of the original DDSF architecture.

7.1 Real-Time Controllable Synthesis

One of the many advantages of using a DDSF-based model, particularly a model that incorporates a signal processor specifically designed to generate a particular type of sound, is its efficiency. More precisely, because the strong inductive bias introduced by the signal processor reduces the need for the model to learn overly complex patterns, the model’s size can remain relatively small.

A smaller model, in terms of the number of parameters and layers, offers several benefits. For instance, it requires less training compared to larger models. Another advantage is that if the model is sufficiently small, it can be embedded into a real-time environment, such as Pure Data (PD), MAX/MSP, or even as a VST plugin. This has already been demonstrated in previous work. For example, the original DDSF model was later integrated into a VST plugin, and many other Torch-based models have been successfully ported to PD and MAX/MSP using the open-source object `nn_tilde`, developed at IRCAM and publicly available in the GitHub repository `nn_tilde`.

In particular, if a model like the ones proposed in this thesis is translated into a real-time environment, it would be capable of generating an infinite texture sound—specifically, the one it was trained to create—with controllable parameters. These parameters would be determined by the encoder during training. For instance, one could create water sounds and naturally control their spectral mean, rather than manipulating a pre-recorded sound. Similarly, a chimney texture sound could be generated, with its activity over time controlled by adjusting the rate parameter. The possibilities are vast and depend entirely on the dataset and encoder

used during training.

Although implementing the real-time synthesis approach described here extends beyond the scope of this thesis, we have left it as a direction for future work.

7.2 Timbre Transfer

The application that arguably made the first DDSF model so popular was its capacity to perform "timbre transfer." In the original paper [Engel et al., 2020], the authors explain that timbre transfer is an example application of their model, where they drive the model using features from an unexpected input. For example, they use the pitch and loudness of a voice as inputs for a model trained on a violin dataset. The result is that the timbre of the violin model is "transferred" to the voice signal.

In practice, this type of timbre transfer is merely a consequence of a highly biased model. For example, in the case just discussed, the model was trained on a violin dataset, and as a result, the model is so heavily biased toward this task that the only sounds it can synthesize are those of a violin. Since the model is driven by two features of a sound rather than the actual sound, these features can be computed from any reasonable (pitched) sound, creating the illusion of timbre transfer. This is particularly interesting because it suggests that when the input has a nature where pitch is less meaningful, the timbre transfer effect becomes less evident.

For the models proposed in this thesis, the process is analogous but less semantically meaningful. On one hand, the models proposed in this thesis have been designed to closely match the original DDSF architecture. Consequently, a well-trained model will exhibit the properties of a highly biased model that can be driven by a limited set of parameters. Therefore, for example, one can use a fire sound as the input for a water model and achieve some sort of timbre transfer. However, the results are not as interpretable as those in the pitched scenario. This is primarily because pitch and loudness are extremely meaningful features for pitched sounds. When a voice melody is run through a violin model, we can still easily perceive some resemblance to the original sound, even though we are actually hearing a synthesized violin sound. This is not as true for texture sounds unless both the input and output share a meaningful feature that was used during the training phase. One might think that the spectral centroid is a feature with this property, but by itself, it is not nearly as meaningful as pitch is for pitched sounds, as discussed in Section 5.2.

Nevertheless, some examples of running unexpected sounds through the model, or Timbre Transfer, can be found in Section 8.4.

Chapter 8

Implementation and Results

In this chapter, the results of all the experiments conducted throughout this research are presented and discussed. First, the implementation of all the algorithms proposed in this thesis is briefly reviewed. Next, the signal processors and algorithms introduced in Chapter 3 are tested. Following that, the loss function introduced in Chapter 4 is studied and employed to evaluate its potential for distinguishing texture sounds. Finally, the results obtained from training the models introduced in Chapter 6 and some variations of these models are discussed.

Remark 8.1 (Warning!) *Reporting synthesis results in a manuscript based on perceptual constraints, such as those underlying the `TextStat` loss function and the principles behind both the `SubEnv Synth` and the `P-VAE Synth`, can be misleading and counterproductive. In this regard, this section attempts to report the results as accurately as possible; however, the most important aspect is actually listening to the resulting sounds. To do so, we refer to the GitHub repository `ddsp_textures_thesis` (see *Preliminary Notes* for details).*

In this context, we believe that the best way to evaluate the models proposed here is through subjective evaluation. More on this can be found in Section 8.4.

8.1 Implementation

All the algorithms presented in this thesis are implemented in a GitHub repository called `ddsp_textures`. The implementation of these algorithms is compatible with the PyTorch package to ensure easy integration into a deep learning environment.

In addition, several essential functions required for the algorithms presented in this thesis are also implemented in a manner compatible with the PyTorch environment, as they are not included in the package. Some examples of these functions are as follows:

1. *ERB, Linear, and Log Filterbanks*: Filterbanks were extremely important for

this thesis, so a PyTorch-compatible implementation was necessary. The code implementation itself was inspired by the open-source Numpy implementation available in the GitHub repository `py_bank`, which in turn was fully based on the Matlab implementation proposed by McDermott and Simoncelli in their original work [McDermott and Simoncelli, 2011].

2. *Discrete Hilbert Transform*: Used primarily to compute amplitude envelopes and is fully based on the Numpy implementation.
3. *Onset Detection*: Used to compute features for some texture sounds. It is conceptually inspired by the onset detection algorithm implemented in Librosa.

Additionally, modules within the package have corresponding helper notebooks that include examples of how to run every function in the repository, including synthesis, resynthesis, and training features.

The resulting package was used to run all the experiments in this thesis, and it is cloned in the first line of every notebook in the `ddsp_textures_thesis` repository.

8.2 Signal Processors Testing

Both synthesizers introduced in this thesis were designed to be used as DDSP signal processors. As such, they can be considered differentiable functions that map sets of parameters into actual sound signals. As discussed in Subsections 3.1.2 and 3.2.2, this does not mean that they can only be used in deep learning environments. In this section, both synthesizers are tested outside of their typical use cases through various synthesis experiments.

8.2.1 SubEnv Synth Testing

In this subsection, two experiments are briefly discussed to demonstrate both the potential of the `SubEnv Synth` and to empirically validate a claim made in Section 3.1 regarding seed independence.

Resynthesis Task

The `SubEnv Synth` can theoretically be used to resynthesize any sound using appropriate parameters. However, due to its noisy nature, the only types of sounds that can be successfully synthesized with a low number of parameters are noisy sounds.

Several experiments were conducted in this context, all following the same approach. First, a set of parameters was chosen by hand to run Algorithm 3. This results in a set of parameters that are used as the input to Algorithm 2, which outputs a signal. This process was done 100 times for different segments of the same audio file and the loss statistics are reported in Table 2. Additionally, some of the resulting spectrograms can be seen in Figure 13.

Sound	Parameters	Compression	TextStat Loss	Multiscale Loss
Fire	$N = 32768, N_F = 24, N_P = 512$	266.67%	1.02 ± 0.2	35.29 ± 3.73
Water	$N = 32768, N_F = 16, N_P = 256$	800%	2.04 ± 0.1	19.66 ± 1.53

Table 2: Resynthesis results using the SubEnv Synth. In any case, an ERB filterbank was used. Compression correspond to the ratio of samples in the target signal to parameters used by the synthesizer. The mean and standard deviance of the losses are reported for a set of 100 resynthesized segments of the original sounds. For details regarding the sound materials used see Preliminary Notes. The parameters of the TextStat loss function are $\alpha = (10, 50, 100, 100, 100)$, $\beta = 9$ and the scales for the Multiscale Spectrogram loss are $s \in \{128, 256, 512, 1024, 2048, 4096\}$.

Figure 13: Spectrograms of some resynthesized sounds using the SubEnv Synth.

Seed Exploration

One of the `SubEnv Synth` inputs is a precomputed seed. Seeds are computed based on white noise, and there are infinitely many of them. In this experiment, three precomputed seeds are used to synthesize the same sound with the same parameters. The length of the audio to resynthesize is fixed to 5 seconds, and the losses are computed for frames using the same frame size that was used to resynthesize the sound. The statistics regarding the results are summarized in Table 3 and show that, even though seeds introduce deterministic randomness, different seeds yield perceptually almost identical sounds for the texture sounds studied.

Sound	Seed 1 vs Seed 2		Seed 1 vs Seed 3		Seed 2 vs Seed 3	
	TextStat	Multiscale	TextStat	Multiscale	TextStat	Multiscale
Fire	0.56 ± 0.02	4.41 ± 0.05	0.56 ± 0.02	4.42 ± 0.06	0.56 ± 0.02	4.41 ± 0.05
Water	0.59 ± 0.02	4.56 ± 0.06	0.62 ± 0.03	4.6 ± 0.06	0.6 ± 0.02	4.56 ± 0.05

Table 3: `SubEnv Synth` seed independence results. In any case, an ERB filterbank was used. The mean and standard deviance of the losses per segments are reported for 3 pairs of resynthesized sounds using different seeds. For details regarding the sound materials used see Preliminary Notes. The parameters of the `TextStat` loss function are $\alpha = (10, 50, 100, 100, 100)$, $\beta = 9$ and the scales for the Multiscale Spectrogram loss are $s \in \{128, 256, 512, 1024, 2048, 4096\}$.

8.2.2 P-VAE Synth Testing

In this subsection, the algorithms related to the P-VAE `Synth` are explored. First, Algorithm 4 is run using a large set of parameters. Then, the results concerning the training of a particular type of VAE are presented as an example of an Atom generator. Finally, the time-stamped signal generator algorithm and the previously trained VAE are used together as inputs for the P-VAE `Synth` to explore its synthesis possibilities.

Time-Stamped Signal Generator Testing

To assess the performance of Algorithm 4, two experiments were conducted. First, we verified that the algorithm produces time-stamped signals with the input rate, on average. Then, we computed and displayed several time-stamped signals for different combinations of rates and α parameters for visualization purposes.

To test the rate parameter, we fixed the rates $\lambda \in \{1, 2, 4, 8, 16, 32, 64, 128, 256\}$ and computed 100 time-stamped signals with a random $\alpha > 0$ parameter. We then calculated the average rate for each case. The results obtained demonstrate that the algorithm functions as expected and can be found in Table 8.2.2.

Additionally, a series of time-stamped signals were generated using different parameters for visual exploration. The results can be seen in Figure 14.

Target rate (λ)	Theoretical rate ($f_s \cdot p$)	Empirical rate ($\mu \pm \sigma$)
1	1	1.03 ± 0.99
2	2	2.01 ± 1.38
4	4	4.07 ± 1.98
8	8	8.07 ± 2.85
16	16	16.09 ± 3.83
32	31.99	31.89 ± 5.47
64	63.45	63.47 ± 7.98
128	127.81	127.53 ± 11.06
256	255.26	255.98 ± 15.77

Table 4: The average rate accuracy of the time-stamped signal generator was tested with 100 time-stamped signal generated using Algorithm 4 with $N = f_s = 44100$. Theoretical and empirical rates are rounded to two decimal places.

Figure 14: Time-stamped signal generation using all combination of parameters $(\lambda, \alpha) \in \{2, 5, 10, 25, 50\} \times \{0.01, 0.05, 0.5, 1, 10\}$.

Figure 15: Training loss of the Atom generator VAE.

Atom Generator Example

The definition of the Atom generator presented here (see Definition 3.8) is quite broad, allowing for various methods of generation. In this subsection, we present the results of one atom generator created using a VAE-like architecture. For details regarding the architecture, see Appendix A.

The atom generator was trained on 4 minutes of audio corresponding to an augmented version of a river recording (see Preliminary Notes). The model was trained to encode audio frames of 16384 samples at $f_s = 44100$ into a latent space $\mathbb{Y} = \mathbb{R}^2$, and then decode them into signals of the same length using a combination of MLPs and the `SubEnv Synth`. It was trained with the `TextStat` loss function along with the Kullback-Leibler loss function to ensure that the encoded dataset follows a normal distribution. The training losses are shown in Figure 15, demonstrating that the model was able to learn the task. However, the results obtained are not of the highest quality, and some parts of the latent space produce atoms that resemble filtered noise.

The resulting model has the capability to generate sound atoms from the latent space. Specifically, for any $Y \in \mathbb{Y}$, we can generate an atom through $D(Y)$, where D corresponds to the decoder of the model. The latent space was explored in detail by using a lattice of vectors in $[0, 1] \times [0, 1]$ to generate sounds, as shown in Figure 16.

Additional to the model previously discussed, the same architecture was trained on a dataset of fire sounds, however the results were considerably worse. This might

Figure 16: A lattice of points in the latent space $\mathbb{Y} = \mathbb{R}^2$ is decoded, and their spectrograms are plotted.

Figure 17: In this example, $K = 40$ points in the latent space $\mathbb{Y} = \mathbb{R}^2$ were used to generate atoms of sound of size 16384. These atoms were then combined with a 10 seconds long time-stamped signal with parameters $\lambda = 15$ and $\alpha = 0.25$. All of this was done through the P-VAE Synth.

be because of the target frame size being too small for the TextStat loss function to capture the nature of the fire sounds.

Exploratory Synthesis

With both the time-stamped signal generator and the atom generator implemented, we can now use them as inputs to run the P-VAE Synth.

A series of examples using different K , M , N , and Y parameters were computed. Note that the VAE decoder trained in the previous section generates atoms of fixed size $M = 16384$ samples. However, by simple truncation, one can generate smaller atoms, so M can be adjusted accordingly. Additionally, since $Y = \{Y_1, \dots, Y_K\}$ is a sequence of vectors in $\mathbb{Y} = \mathbb{R}^2$, we can create sounds that navigate through the latent space in interesting and visually observable ways. One instance of this exploration through the latent space can be seen in Figure 17.

8.3 Loss Function Testing

We are interested in testing the proficiency of the TextStat loss function. To do this, we aim to examine two aspects:

1. Given two reasonably different texture sound signals, say $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^N$, will the loss between them, $\mathcal{L}_{\alpha, \beta}(x, y)$, be large?
2. Given two reasonably similar texture sound signals $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^N$, will the loss

between them, $\mathcal{L}_{\alpha,\beta}(x, y)$, be small?

Of course, "large" and "small" are not precise adjectives. However, by fixing $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}^5$, one can normalize the results to obtain precise numbers for comparison.

Answering these questions appropriately requires optimally selecting α and conducting exhaustive testing. While these tasks were beyond the scope of this thesis, we propose a method for choosing α optimally in Appendix B and present some exploratory research to provide a preliminary answer to the questions posed.

To conduct this exploratory research, we segmented two recordings of equal length, corresponding to different types of texture sounds. This resulted in two disjoint sets of equal cardinality: $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots\}$ and $Y = \{y_1, y_2, \dots\}$. We then computed the following statistics:

$$\mu(a | B) = \frac{1}{|B|} \sum_{b \in B} \mathcal{L}_{\alpha,\beta}(a, b), \quad (8.1)$$

for $a \in X \cup Y$ and $B \in \{X, Y\}$. The statistic $\mu(a | B)$ represents the average loss between a segment a and the set of segments B . Therefore, one would expect both $\mu(x_j | X) \ll \mu(x_j | Y)$ and $\mu(y_j | Y) \ll \mu(y_j | X)$, as this would imply that the loss function is capable of distinguishing, on average, sounds from the datasets X and Y .

The results from this experiment are shown in Figure 18, demonstrating that, on average, the loss function with parameters $\alpha = (10, 50, 100, 100, 100)$, $\beta = 9$, is capable of distinguishing between water and fire sounds without any issues. It is also interesting to note that the distances between segments of fire sounds are, on average, greater than those between segments of water sounds. This can be explained by the variability in the number of crackling sounds that can appear within a segment of fire, whereas water sounds are much more stable.

It is also important to note that an experiment conducted indirectly throughout this research involved using the `TextStat` loss function as the actual loss function when training all the models in this thesis. The results generally indicate that this loss function helps the model learn to synthesize texture sounds effectively. In contrast, recreating the experiments with other loss functions, such as the Multiscale Spectrogram loss function, typically yields results that are correct in their frequency content but completely miss amplitude envelope information, resulting in sounds that resemble filtered noise.

8.4 DDSP model

For the DDSP model, we used the architecture introduced in 6.1 with several combinations of features and model parameters. In this section we will focus on a particular model trained to synthesize water texture sounds, however many other models were trained and can be found in the GitHub repository (see Preliminary Notes). First, we will discuss how the dataset was generated. Second, what model

Figure 18: Boxplots of the mean distances between segments and sets of segments, in that order. For example the first bar (from the left) symbolizes the interquartile range and median of the distances $\mu(x | Y)$, where $x \in X = \{\text{Fire segments}\}$ and $Y = \{\text{Water segments}\}$. All the computations were done using a ERB filterbank with $N_F = 24$ and segments of around 3 seconds of audio.

parameters were used. Third, we will discuss how the model was trained. Fourth, we will talk about how the model was and should be evaluated. And finally, some sound examples are reported.

8.4.1 Dataset

In order to train a model on water sound synthesis, we used a water recording that was manipulated in order to make it mono and 30 seconds long. Then, with the purpose of augmentate the data, this snippet was further manipulated to make it 5 minutes and so that it has way more spectrum variance. This was achieved using a pitch shifting algorithm implemented in Ableton. The resulting audio was segmented and their spectral mean and standard deviance were extracted. Finally, this set of annotated segments was divided into three parts, the training set used solely for training, the validation set used for fine tuning and avoid overfitting, and the test set used to test the model in the resynthesis task.

8.4.2 Model Parameters

The models were initialized with the combination of parameters in Table 5.

Model ID	Target	MLPs		SubEnv Synth	
	Frame Size (N)	Hidden Size (h_s)	Depth (d)	Number of Filters (N_F)	Number of parameters (N_P)
1	8192	256	2	16	256
2	8192	256	3	16	256
3	16384	512	2	16	512
4	16384	512	3	16	512

Table 5: The table shows model configuration parameters including target frame sizes, MLP hidden sizes and depths, filterbank size and number of parameters per band. The compression given by these parameters is 200% in every case.

8.4.3 Training

In order to train the model, the segments were arranged in batches of size 16 and the loss function consisted of a sum between the **TextStat** loss function and a ℓ^2 -regularizer that compare the features extracted with the ones in the output signal of the model. More precisely

$$\mathcal{L}(x, \hat{x}) = \mathcal{L}_{\alpha, \beta}(x, \hat{x}) + \|(f_1, f_2) - (\hat{f}_1, \hat{f}_2)\|_2,$$

where x is the input target, \hat{x} is the output signal of the model, f_1, f_2 are the features extracted from x and \hat{f}_1, \hat{f}_2 are the features extracted from \hat{x} .

As it seemed to work well, the same $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}^5, \beta \in \mathbb{R}$ used in the last section were used. Additionally, the features were normalized so that the ℓ^2 -regularizer is in a comparable scale with the **TextStat** loss.

All models in Table 5 were trained with both regularization and not regularization. Some training curves examples can be found in Figures 19 and 20.

8.4.4 Evaluation

After training, the models were retrained with the validation set for a lower number of epochs for fine tuning and then they were evaluated using the test set. The result of this process can be seen in Table 6, and several sound examples can be found in the GitHub Repository `ddsp_textures_thesis`.

The results show that, in general, all models learned to characterize the timbre of the texture sound in terms of the **TextStat** loss function, whether or not regularization was used. On the other hand, the Multiscale Spectrogram loss function shows that, on average, regularization helps to better characterize the spectrum. This is unsurprising, as the regularizer pushes the model to match the features of the input with those of the output, and in these cases, these features corresponded to spectral statistics.

Figure 19: Training curve for some DDSP models without regularization.

Model ID	Regularization (True/False)	TextStat Loss ($\mu \pm \sigma$)	Multiscale Loss ($\mu \pm \sigma$)
1	True	0.78 ± 0.06	6.83 ± 0.83
1	False	0.78 ± 0.07	11.13 ± 1.09
2	True	0.77 ± 0.06	6.713 ± 0.83
2	False	0.78 ± 0.06	11.46 ± 1.08
3	True	0.78 ± 0.06	7.27 ± 1.00
3	False	0.77 ± 0.05	10.81 ± 1.06
4	True	0.78 ± 0.06	7.52 ± 0.97
4	False	0.77 ± 0.05	10.98 ± 1.086

Table 6: Mean and standard deviations of the losses given by the trained models in the test set. The parameters of the `TextStat` loss function are $\alpha = (10, 50, 100, 100, 100)$, $\beta = 9$ and the scales for the Multiscale Spectrogram loss are $s \in \{128, 256, 512, 1024, 2048, 4096\}$.

Losses curve for model with parameters $N = 16384$, $d = 2$ and with regularization

Losses curve for model with parameters $N = 16384$, $d = 3$ and with regularization

Losses curve for model with parameters $N = 8192$, $d = 2$ and with regularization

Losses curve for model with parameters $N = 8192$, $d = 3$ and with regularization

Figure 20: Training curve for some DDSF models without regularization.

If one looks at Table 6, one may be tempted to conclude that a shallower model is not much different from a deeper one, given their similar validation losses. However, this observation underscores the limitations of using objective validation techniques to evaluate a generative model designed to synthesize texture sounds. While the validation losses used here are reasonable characterizations of the signal, the audio produced by deeper models generally sounds less synthetic. This suggests that certain important features are not being captured by the loss functions.

Although objective evaluation using a test set is customary, we believe that the most effective way to assess the performance of the model would be through some form of subjective evaluation. This belief is rooted in the model’s intrinsic goal, which is to resynthesize a texture sound by replicating its statistical properties. Objectively evaluating this goal presents several challenges:

1. *Interpreting statistical thresholds:* As done here, we can always use the `TextStat` loss function to measure the average error produced by the model on the test set. However, this approach lacks strong interpretability because there has been insufficient research into this loss function, and we don’t yet know what constitutes "good" thresholds. Additionally, these numbers are heavily influenced by various constraints, such as the frame size and the number of filters used. Therefore, arguing solely based on these metrics may not be productive.
2. *Incompatibility with other losses:* Of course, one could use alternative loss functions, as was done in this study with the Multiscale Spectrogram loss function. However, this may be counterproductive in most cases, as the goal of these models is not to generate a sound identical to the input but rather one that is statistically equivalent and thus perceptually similar. Many loss functions are based on the notion of perfect reconstruction according to a given auditory perception model, which diverges from the objectives of our model.
3. *Neglecting the ecological approach:* Even if we had a loss function that provided a solid point of comparison, we cannot ignore that while we are using statistical methods, the ultimate goal is to create sounds perceived as originating from the same source. The goal is not to reproduce the exact same sound, spectrum, or statistics, but rather to generate the same type of sound so that humans perceive them as the same event. Arguably, this can only be effectively evaluated through subjective means.

This thesis has addressed all the technical challenges related to the proposed models. However, as subjective evaluation falls outside its scope, we have decided to leave it for future work.

8.4.5 Sound Examples

Each model was tested on three tasks. First, each model was used to resynthesize a texture sound similar to the one used for training. Next, the features of the

same sound were manipulated to control the spectral centroid of the resynthesis process. Finally, features from sounds outside the model's scope were used to drive the synthesis.

In the resynthesis task, all models demonstrated varying degrees of success, being able to synthesize a water sound that was synthetic and somewhat more intense than the input sounds.

Regarding the control task, only the deep and regularized models effectively controlled the output features of the synthesized sound. This outcome was expected, given that only the regularized models performed well using the Multiscale Spectrogram loss function.

Finally, features from two sounds that were entirely unknown to the model were computed and used to drive the synthesis process. These sounds were a recording of an adult walking and a beatbox recording (for details on these sounds see Preliminary Notes). They were selected because they represent texture sounds with very intense amplitude envelopes, whereas the water sounds used for training had relatively stable amplitude envelopes, thus presenting a natural challenge for the model.

The results of the timbre transfer are particularly interesting in the case of the "walking recording." The amplitude envelope of the footsteps was well captured by models trained on smaller frames, preserving some of the transients of the steps. However, the sound of each step was entirely replaced by snippets of what could be described as a very intense river. It is also noteworthy that although the footsteps had a relatively stable rhythm, the inherent randomness of the model caused the new "water footsteps" to lack the well-defined rhythm of the original input. On the other hand, the transients of the beatbox sounds were too rapid to be captured by any of the models. The output is no longer recognizable as the original input and can be described as a synthetic river with significant fluctuations.

8.5 Stochastic-DDSP Model Results

The Stochastic-DDSP model was implemented in the same GitHub repository as the original DDSP model. However, as of now, this model has not been able to train properly, and further investigation is needed to resolve the underlying issues.

More specifically, the primary challenge during training is that, regardless of the parameters selected, the training loss inevitably becomes NaN at a certain point. This behavior suggests instability in the model's learning process. Upon closer examination, it was determined that the problem originates with the encoder's hyperparameters, which eventually diverge. Although weight-clamping techniques were applied in an attempt to stabilize the training, these efforts were ultimately unsuccessful.

This persistent issue has led me to hypothesize that the problem is related to the overall depth of the neural network. While both the encoder and decoder were designed to be relatively shallow to avoid overfitting and reduce computational com-

plexity, the signal processor, the P-VAE `Synth`, introduces significant depth due to its reliance on another pretrained model. This additional depth may be causing gradients to vanish or explode, leading to the observed training instability.

To address this, future work will focus on modifying the architecture of the pretrained VAE to reduce its depth. This adjustment aims to create a more balanced and trainable model by ensuring that all components of the network work harmoniously together. Moreover, alternative strategies, such as gradient clipping or reinitializing specific layers during training, could be explored to further enhance stability.

This investigation into model depth and stability is crucial for the successful deployment of the Stochastic-DDSP model in practical applications. More details on the proposed modifications and their expected impact are discussed in Chapter 9, where potential avenues for future research are also outlined.

8.6 Other models

After extensive experimentation, several variations were made to the architectures proposed here in an effort to improve performance. While these variations do not directly correspond to the exact work presented in this thesis, they are strongly based on it. Notably, the sound synthesis results have improved considerably, especially for certain types of sounds that the previous models struggled to synthesize effectively.

8.6.1 Model variations

There are two main variations between the previously discussed models and the ones presented here. The first variation involves using larger windows. This approach was initially not considered because the `TextStat` loss function had not been fully optimized in terms of computational complexity. As a result, training larger models was beyond the scope of what could be achieved within the timeframe of this thesis. Over time, the loss function has been significantly improved, and by the time of submission of this thesis, although it remains considerably slower than other loss functions, it is approximately three times faster than its original implementation.

The second difference between the models proposed in this thesis and the subsequent variations pertains to the feature extraction process and the design of the encoder layer. Section 5.2 provides a list of the multi-purpose features used by the models introduced in this thesis. However, these features proved to be too generic and did not adequately capture the characteristics of certain sounds, such as fire crackling. To address this issue, a new feature was introduced: the energy of the subband decomposition. More precisely, let $F = \{f_j\}_{j=1}^{N_F}$ represent the filterbank used by the model. This feature is computed as follows:

$$e_F(x) = (\|f_1 * x\|, \|f_2 * x\|, \dots, \|f_{N_F} * x\|) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_F}.$$

This feature is valuable for two reasons. First, it aligns well with the model, providing a wealth of meaningful information. Second, when N_F is sufficiently large, this vector contains enough information to estimate both the spectral mean and the spectral standard deviation.

The transition from using single features to extracting feature vectors was not compatible with the encoders introduced in Chapter 5. Consequently, the encoder architecture had to be modified to accommodate this new feature extraction process, and in the process, different types of architectures were tested.

Before discussing the examples, it is important to note that while this new feature provides significant information that helps the model learn more complex timbres, it is less semantically meaningful. In other words, controlling this feature is less intuitive for humans.

8.6.2 Sound examples and evaluation

Four models were successfully trained using the variations proposed in the previous subsection. Two of these models are designed for water sounds, and the other two are for fire sounds.

All four models were tested on both the resynthesis and timbre transfer tasks. For the resynthesis task, the input sounds included the "walking recording" used in previous models. Additionally, fire sounds were used as inputs for the water models, and vice versa (for details on the sounds, see Preliminary Notes).

The water models showed significant improvement in the resynthesis task, producing sounds that are notably more natural than those obtained with previous models. Among the fire models, one was able to resynthesize recognizable fire crackling sounds, while the other produced a sound with transients similar to the original fire sounds, but with a somewhat blurry quality. The resynthesis task was evaluated using the same parameters as for the DDSP models proposed earlier, and the results were considerably better than those obtained with previous models. Details are presented in Table 7.

Model name	TextStat Loss ($\mu \pm \sigma$)	Multiscale Loss ($\mu \pm \sigma$)
fire_long_mlp	0.71 \pm 0.14	11.57 \pm 1.47
water_long_mlp	0.57 \pm 0.01	5.73 \pm 0.44
fire_long_gru	0.69 \pm 0.09	12.65 \pm 1.44
water_long_gru	0.58 \pm 0.01	6.03 \pm 0.50

Table 7: Mean and standard deviations of the losses given by the trained models on the test set. The parameters of the TextStat loss function are $\alpha = (10, 50, 100, 100, 100)$, $\beta = 9$ and the scales for the Multiscale Spectrogram loss are $s \in \{128, 256, 512, 1024, 2048, 4096\}$.

In the timbre transfer task, the models, being trained to generate larger chunks of audio, are not as adept at capturing the rapid transients of walking or fire sounds compared to previous models. However, some of the amplitude envelopes are still captured, albeit in a smoother manner. Due to the improved quality of the models, the resulting sounds are generally more natural than those produced by previous models.

Chapter 9

Conclusions and Future Work

This chapter provides a summary of the conclusions regarding the models and discussions presented throughout this thesis.

9.1 About the SubEnv and P-VAE Synthesizers

In this thesis, we introduced two signal processors specifically designed for synthesizing texture sounds: the `SubEnv Synth` and the `P-VAE Synth`. These processors were designed with differentiability in mind, allowing them to be integrated seamlessly into DDSP-based architectures. Both synthesizers were implemented to be compatible with PyTorch, leveraging automatic differentiation to facilitate their use in deep learning applications.

The theoretical underpinnings of these synthesizers, including their differentiability properties, were discussed in detail. Empirical results demonstrated their effectiveness in synthesizing texture sounds. Notably, the `SubEnv Synth` was shown to accurately resynthesize various texture sounds, achieving high precision and generating compact representations.

9.2 About the TextStat Loss Function

The thesis explores the desired properties for a loss function aimed at distinguishing texture sounds. Inspired by the work of McDermott and Simoncelli, we introduced the `TextStat` loss function, which was theoretically examined and designed to meet these needs.

The `TextStat` loss function was implemented in a manner compatible with PyTorch, utilizing automatic differentiation to ensure integration with deep learning frameworks. It was tested on a small dataset to evaluate its effectiveness, demonstrating satisfactory performance. The loss function was subsequently applied in deep learning models, where it significantly contributed to the models' ability to learn texture

sound synthesis tasks.

9.3 About the DDSP and Stochastic-DDSP Architectures

This thesis presented two DDSP-based architectures: one designed to work with the `SubEnv Synth` and the other with the `P-VAE Synth`. Detailed discussions and implementations of these architectures in PyTorch were provided.

The architecture utilizing the `SubEnv Synth` was successfully trained on several small datasets. We provided a detailed account of one such model, including training specifics and sound examples, showcasing its performance.

Conversely, the architecture employing the `P-VAE Synth` encountered difficulties in learning the resynthesis task. The exact reasons for the training challenges remain unclear, but it is hypothesized that the complexity introduced by the VAE module in the `P-VAE Synth` may be a contributing factor.

Additionally, some variations of these models and their results were briefly discussed to provide further insights into the performance and limitations of these architectures.

9.4 Future Work

Throughout this thesis, several avenues for future research have been proposed. This section summarizes these suggestions and introduces some new insights that have emerged from testing.

9.4.1 Optimization of the `TextStat` loss function

One key area for future work is the optimization of the parameter α in the `TextStat` loss function. Identifying the optimal value for α is crucial for maximizing the effectiveness of this loss function in distinguishing texture sounds. While determining this optimal value is complex, a theoretical approach to this problem is discussed in Appendix B.

Additionally, understanding the perceptual impact of the `TextStat` loss function is vital. This could be achieved by assessing the thresholds of general agreement through subjective evaluation methods. Such assessments would enhance our understanding of the loss function's practical implications.

9.4.2 Reconsidering the Use of VAEs in Stochastic DDSP Architectures

The challenges encountered with training the Stochastic DDSP architecture, suggest that the complexity introduced by the VAE module in the P-VAE Synth may be a strong contributing factor. Reconsidering the use of a VAE as an atom generator is recommended. The broad definition of an atom generator, as described in Section 3.2, allows for the exploration of simpler functions that might be more effective.

9.4.3 Exploring Model Variations and New Features

While the DDSP model presented in this thesis achieved some success, exploratory variations of this model have yielded significantly better results. One notable variation that substantially improved performance is discussed in Section 8.6. Further research is needed to explore this direction and to incorporate new features that could enhance the model’s performance to its full potential.

9.4.4 Improving Meaningfulness of the Evaluation Process

As discussed during the evaluation of the different models in 8, objective evaluation alone does not appear to capture all aspects regarding the timbre of texture sounds. Therefore, it is important to consider incorporating subjective evaluation techniques in future models, as these are more likely to capture the ecological understanding of texture sounds.

9.4.5 Real-Time Implementation of Trained Models

To increase the impact of this research, implementing the best-trained models in a real-time environment would be valuable. This can be facilitated using the `nn ~ object`, as discussed in Chapter 7. Real-time implementation would offer practical applications and broaden the scope of the research findings.

Appendix A

Training an atom generator

An atom generator can be made in multiple ways, one of which consists of training a VAE. In this chapter, a simple but effective way of training a VAE whose decoder can be used as an atom generator is introduced.

Using VAE architectures in audio is not trivial, since the temporal nature of sound is not inherently captured by its default components. One way of dealing with this is by adding a layer at the end of the architecture that is meant to output audio from a handful of parameters. This idea shouldn't be surprising, since it is what characterizes any DDSF architecture. Since in this thesis we have introduced a fully differentiable signal processor that is meant to create texture sounds, we shall use it as the last layer of our architecture.

More precisely, this VAE-like architecture consists of:

1. An encoder that takes the input, typically a handful of audio features, and encodes them into a pair of vectors $(\mu, \sigma) \in \mathbb{Y} \times \mathbb{Y}$;
2. A reparameterization (stochastic) layer that transforms $(\mu, \sigma) \in \mathbb{Y} \times \mathbb{Y}$ into $Z = \mu + \epsilon \odot \sigma \in \mathbb{Y}$, where $\epsilon \sim N(0, \text{Id}_{\dim(\mathbb{Y})})$;
3. A decoder that takes the latent representation Z and outputs a set of parameters P ;
4. A map that uses the parameters P to generate an audio signal through the `SubEnv-Synth`.

In order to train an architecture like the one just proposed, one would need a loss function and a dataset of sound atoms. Fortunately, in this thesis, a loss function designed for texture sounds is introduced, so we shall use `TextStat` for this task. To create a dataset, it is enough to take a set of audio segments from a sufficiently long target texture sound. In our experiments, these segments were selected by focusing on parts where an onset was detected. For fire sounds, this resulted in a set of sound

Figure 21: Atom generator VAE architecture.

atoms that were, for the most part, short signals containing a crackling sound. For water sounds, on the other hand, this resulted in atoms containing snippets of sound where the water was particularly excited. The latter resulted in a dataset that biases any model trained on it to generate overly excited water sounds, which is not ideal but will work just fine for the purposes of this thesis.

For a graphic representation of the architecture just presented, see Figure 21.

Appendix B

Loss function optimization

As discussed in 8.3, we are interested in the following two properties:

1. Given two reasonably different texture sound signals, say $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^N$, the loss between them, $\mathcal{L}_{\alpha,\beta}(x, y)$, is maximized.
2. Given two reasonably similar texture sound signals $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^N$, the loss between them, $\mathcal{L}_{\alpha,\beta}(x, y)$, is minimized.

Finding an optimal $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}^5$ such that these two properties hold is no easy task. One way to achieve this is by solving an optimization problem. More precisely, let's assume that we have a dataset of texture sounds D that is partitioned into N_C classes of sounds that are similar to each other:

$$D = \bigsqcup_{j=1}^{N_C} D_j.$$

Then, one would be interested in the following optimization problem (with Karush-Kuhn-Tucker constraints):

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \operatorname{argmin}_{\alpha} \left(\sum_{j=1}^C \sum_{x,y \in D_j} \frac{\mathcal{L}_{\alpha,\beta}(x, y)}{|D_j|^2} + \sum_{j=1}^C \sum_{x \in D_j, y \in D \setminus D_j} \frac{\mathcal{L}_{\alpha,\beta}(x, y)^{-1}}{|D_j| \cdot |D \setminus D_j|} \right) \\ \sum_{j=1}^5 \alpha_j = 1 \\ \alpha_j \geq 0, \quad j = 1, \dots, 5 \end{array} \right. ,$$

where $|A|$ represents the cardinality of A .

Solving this problem requires a well-curated dataset of texture sounds and substantial computational power, so this will be left for future work.

Bibliography

- J Antognini, M Hoffman, and RJ Weiss. Synthesizing diverse, high-quality audio textures. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1806.08002*, 2018.
- S. O. Arik, H. Jun, and G. Diamos. Fast Spectrogram Inversion Using Multi-Head Convolutional Neural Networks. *IEEE Signal Processing Letters*, 26(1):94–98, Jan 2019. doi: 10.1109/LSP.2018.2880284.
- T. Caelli and B. Julesz. On perceptual analyzers underlying visual texture discrimination: Part i. *Biological Cybernetics*, 28(3):167–175, Sep. 1978. doi: 10.1007/BF00337138.
- Torsten Dau, Birger Kollmeier, and Armin Kohlrausch. Modeling auditory processing of amplitude modulation. i. detection and masking with narrow-band carriers. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 102:2892–2905, 1997.
- Alexandre Defossez, Neil Zeghidour, Nicolas Usunier, Leon Bottou, and Francis Bach. Sing: Symbol-to-Instrument Neural Generator. In S. Bengio, H. Wallach, H. Larochelle, K. Grauman, N. Cesa-Bianchi, and R. Garnett, editors, *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 31*, pages 9041–9051. Curran Associates, Inc., 2018. URL <http://papers.nips.cc/paper/8118-sing-symbol-to-instrument-neural-generator.pdf>.
- R Diaz, B Hayes, C Saitis, G Fazekas, and M Sandler. Rigid-body sound synthesis with differentiable modal resonators. In *ICASSP 2023 - 2023 IEEE Int. Conf. on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing*, 2023.
- Chris Donahue, Julian McAuley, and Miller Puckette. Adversarial Audio Synthesis. In *International Conference on Learning Representations*, 2019. URL <https://openreview.net/forum?id=ByMVTsR5KQ>.
- Jesse Engel, Kumar Krishna Agrawal, Shuo Chen, Ishaan Gulrajani, Chris Donahue, and Adam Roberts. GANSynth: Adversarial Neural Audio Synthesis. In *International Conference on Learning Representations*, 2019. URL <https://openreview.net/forum?id=H1xQVn09FX>.
- Jesse Engel, Lalit Hantrakul, Chenjie Gu, and Adam Roberts. Ddsp: Differentiable digital signal processing. In *International Conference on Learning Representations*, 2020.

- R. Fassel and D. Püschel. *Modulation detection and masking using deterministic and random maskers*, pages 419–429. Universitäts-gesellschaft Oldenburg, Oldenburg, 1993.
- William W. Gaver. How do we hear in the world? explorations in ecological acoustics. *Ecological Psychology*, 5(4):285–313, 1993a.
- William W. Gaver. What in the world do we hear?: An ecological approach to auditory event perception. *Ecological Psychology*, 5(1):1–29, 1993b.
- Brian R. Glasberg and Brian C.J. Moore. Derivation of auditory filter shapes from notched-noise data. *Hearing Research*, 47:103–138, 1990.
- Lamtharn (Hanoi) Hantrakul, Jesse Engel, Adam Roberts, and Chenjie Gu. Fast and flexible neural audio synthesis. In *Proceedings of the 20th International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference*, 2019. URL <https://archives.ismir.net/ismir2019/paper/000063.pdf>.
- Charles R. Harris, K. Jarrod Millman, Stéfan J. van der Walt, Ralf Gommers, Pauli Virtanen, David Cournapeau, Eric Wieser, Julian Taylor, Sebastian Berg, Nathaniel J. Smith, Robert Kern, Matti Picus, Stephan Hoyer, Marten H. van Kerkwijk, Matthew Brett, Allan Haldane, Jaime Fernández del Río, Mark Wiebe, Pearu Peterson, Pierre Gérard-Marchant, Kevin Sheppard, Tyler Reddy, Warren Weckesser, Hameer Abbasi, Christoph Gohlke, and Travis E. Oliphant. Array programming with NumPy. *Nature*, 585(7825):357–362, September 2020. doi: 10.1038/s41586-020-2649-2. URL <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2649-2>.
- Brian Hayes, John Shier, György Fazekas, Andrew McPherson, and Charalampos Saitis. A review of differentiable digital signal processing for music & speech synthesis. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2308.15422*, 2023.
- A. Humeau-Heurtier. Texture feature extraction methods: A survey. *IEEE Access*, 7:8975–9000, Jan. 2019. doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2890743.
- E. Jang, S. Gu, and B. Poole. Categorical reparameterization with gumbel-softmax. *CoRR*, abs/1611.01144, 2016.
- B. Julesz. Visual pattern discrimination. *IRE Transactions on Information Theory*, 8(2):84–92, Feb. 1962. doi: 10.1109/TIT.1962.1057698.
- Nal Kalchbrenner, Erich Elsen, Karen Simonyan, Seb Noury, Norman Casagrande, Edward Lockhart, Florian Stimberg, Aaron van den Oord, Sander Dieleman, and Koray Kavukcuoglu. Efficient Neural Audio Synthesis. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1802.08435*, 2018.
- Jong Wook Kim, Justin Salamon, Peter Li, and Juan Pablo Bello. Crepe: A convolutional representation for pitch estimation. In *2018 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, pages 161–165. IEEE, IEEE, 2018.

- D. P. Kingma and M. Welling. Auto-encoding variational bayes. *CoRR*, abs/1312.6114, 2013. URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/1312.6114>.
- Anton Lundberg. *Data-Driven Procedural Audio: Procedural Engine Sounds Using Neural Audio Synthesis*. Dissertation, 2020. URL <https://urn.kb.se/resolve?urn=urn:nbn:se:kth:diva-280132>.
- C. J. Maddison, A. Mnih, and Y. W. Teh. The concrete distribution: A continuous relaxation of discrete random variables. *CoRR*, abs/1611.00712, 2016.
- Josh H McDermott and Eero P Simoncelli. Sound texture perception via statistics of the auditory periphery: evidence from sound synthesis. *Neuron*, 71(5):926–940, 2011.
- Josh H. McDermott, Andrew J. Oxenham, and Eero P. Simoncelli. Sound texture synthesis via filter statistics. In *2009 IEEE Workshop on Applications of Signal Processing to Audio and Acoustics*, New Paltz, NY, October 2009.
- Josh H McDermott, Michael Schemitsch, and Eero P Simoncelli. Summary statistics in auditory perception. *Nature Neuroscience*, 16(4):493–498, 2013.
- Brian McFee, Matt McVicar, Daniel Faronbi, Iran Roman, Matan Gover, Stefan Balke, Scott Seyfarth, Ayoub Malek, Colin Raffel, Vincent Lostanlen, Benjamin van Niekirk, Dana Lee, Frank Cwitkowitz, Frank Zalkow, Oriol Nieto, Dan Ellis, Jack Mason, Kyungyun Lee, Bea Steers, Emily Halvachs, Carl Thome, Fabian Robert-Stoter, Rachel Bittner, Ziyao Wei, Adam Weiss, Eric Battenberg, Keunwoo Choi, Ryuichi Yamamoto, CJ Carr, Alex Metsai, Stefan Sullivan, Pius Friesch, Asmitha Krishnakumar, Shunsuke Hidaka, Steve Kowalik, Fabian Keller, Dan Mazur, Alexandre Chabot-Leclerc, Curtis Hawthorne, Chandrashekhar Ramaprasad, Myungchul Keum, Juanita Gomez, Will Monroe, Viktor Andreevitch Morozov, Kian Eliasi, nullmightybofo, Paul Biberstein, N. Dorukhan Sergin, Romain Hennequin, Rimvydas Naktinis, beantowel, Taewoon Kim, Jon Petter sen, Joon Lim, Alex Malins, Daro Heren, Stef van der Struijk, Lorenz Nickel, Jackie Wu, Zhen Wang, Tim Gates, Matt Vollrath, Andy Sarroff, Xiao-Ming, Alastair Porter, Seth Kranzler, VoodooHop, Mattia Di Gangi, Helmi Jinoz, Connor Guerrero, Abduttayyeb Mazhar, toddrme2178, Zvi Baratz, Anton Kostin, Xinlu Zhuang, Cash TingHin Lo, Pavel Campr, Eric Semeniuc, Monsij Biswal, Shayenne Moura, Paul Brossier, Hojin Lee, and Waldir Pimenta. *librosa/librosa: 0.10.2.post1*, May 2024. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11192913>.
- Soroush Mehri, Kundan Kumar, Ishaan Gulrajani, Rithesh Kumar, Shubham Jain, Jose Sotelo, Aaron Courville, and Yoshua Bengio. SampleRNN: An Unconditional End-to-End Neural Audio Generation Model. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1612.07837*, 2016.
- Lenny Renault, Remi Mignot, and Axel Roebel. DDS-Piano: a Neural Sound Synthesizer Informed by Instrument Knowledge. *AES - Journal of the Audio Engineering Society Audio-Acoustics-Application*, 71(9):552–565, September 2023. doi: 10.17743/jaes.2022.0102. URL <https://hal.science/hal-04073770>.

- D. F. Rosenthal and H. G. Okuno. *Computational Auditory Scene Analysis*. CRC Press, Boca Raton, FL, 1998.
- Nicholas Saint-Arnaud. Classification of sound textures. Master’s thesis, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Cambridge, MA, Sep. 1995.
- Xavier Serra and Julius Smith. Spectral modeling synthesis: A sound analysis/synthesis system based on a deterministic plus stochastic decomposition. *Computer Music Journal*, 14(4):12–24, Winter 1990.
- Garima Sharma, Karthikeyan Umamathy, and Sridhar Krishnan. Trends in audio texture analysis, synthesis, and applications. *J. Audio Eng. Soc.*, 70(3):108–127, March 2022. doi: 10.17743/jaes.2021.0060.
- Christian J Steinmetz, Nicholas J Bryan, and Joshua D Reiss. Style transfer of audio effects with differentiable signal processing. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2207.08759*, 2022.
- Aaron van den Oord, Sander Dieleman, Heiga Zen, Karen Simonyan, Oriol Vinyals, Alex Graves, Nal Kalchbrenner, Andrew Senior, and Koray Kavukcuoglu. WaveNet: A Generative Model for Raw Audio. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1609.03499*, 2016.
- G. van Rossum. Python tutorial. Technical Report CS-R9526, Centrum voor Wiskunde en Informatica (CWI), Amsterdam, May 1995.
- Yuxuan Wang, RJ Skerry-Ryan, Daisy Stanton, Yonghui Wu, Ron J. Weiss, Navdeep Jaitly, Zongheng Yang, Ying Xiao, Zhifeng Chen, Samy Bengio, et al. Tacotron: Towards End-to-End Speech Synthesis. In *INTERSPEECH*, 2017.
- Lonce Wyse. An audio texture lutherie1. *Annual Art Journal*, 43(54), 2022.
- Luke Wyse and Mohd Huzaifah. Deep learning models for generating audio textures. In *Proceedings of the 2020 Joint Conference on Music Creativity, Sweden*, 2020.
- Chin-Yun Yu and György Fazekas. Singing voice synthesis using differentiable lpc and glottal-flow-inspired wavetables. In *International Society for Music Information Retrieval (ISMIR)*, 2023.